

D6.1

Inventory of existing data sources and formats

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List of Abbreviations / Acronyms

Note: All corpus acronyms are resolved in the corpusTable and will not be added to the following list.

Abbreviation/Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
CIDOC CRM	Comité international pour la documentation Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CLS	Computational Literary Studies
CLS INFRA	Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure
CLSCor	Core ontology for CLS corpora
CoRD	Corpus Resource Database
CRMdig	Conceptual Reference Model digital
D (e.g., D6.1, D5.1)	Deliverable
DH	Digital Humanities
DraCor	Drama Corpora Project
ELTec	European Literary Text Collection
FAIR, FAIR principles	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FRBRoo	Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records object oriented
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ISO codes	International Organisation for Standardisation
LINHD	Laboratorio de Innovación en Humanidades Digitales
LOD	Linked Open Data
M (e.g., M24)	Month
MKM	Metamodel for Corpus Metadata
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ODD	One Document Does it All
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PoS	Part of Speech
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SARI	Swiss Art Research Infrastructure
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol And RDF Query Language
TaDiRAH	Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

WP	Work package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the work done to compile a comprehensive overview of the landscape of literary corpora and sources currently available.

It describes the methodological approach of the work group and analyses the various challenges encountered in the effort to collect information about these resources and consolidate them into a structured form.

Based on an initial inventory of 86 corpora or corpus sets, the report exemplifies their wide variety with respect to structure, context and purpose, and consequently the differing modes of provisioning.

It also proposes a technological path towards making this information searchable via a central discovery catalogue by discussing principal design decisions regarding the data model and the technology stack needed for such a task.

2. Introduction

*"The digital age offers challenges and opportunities for completing research on Europe's multilingual and interconnected literary heritage. At present, the landscape of literary data is diverse and fragmented. Even though many resources are currently available in digital libraries, a lack of standardisation hinders their access and reuse."*¹

The goal of WP6 "Consolidating and preparing data for CLS" is to collect, describe, analyse and consolidate information about European literary corpora (focusing on formats and schemas applied) in an inventory and process this data into a catalogue², to foster the findability of these resources by scholars.

Furthermore, WP6 will aim to provide the necessary transformation tools and workflows allowing to work with the heterogeneous data, by consolidating and re-using existing technical solutions rather than creating something entirely new. All this aims at fostering the FAIRification of literary corpus data, i.e., making it findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable.

The main goal of T6.1 is *"to build an inventory to capture the heterogeneous landscape of data sources and available formats defined by WP5 in relation to the tools and services in the ecosystem to process these."*³ This goal can be divided into three subtasks: collecting the information, devising a data model allowing to capture this information in a structured, coherent manner and developing an application, which implements the data model, contains the collected information and makes it available for exploration. T6.1 is collaborating tightly with and referencing to the tasks and deliverables of the work packages 3, 5, 7 and 8 of the CLS Infra project.

D3.1 "Baseline Methodological user needs analysis" (Schöch et al., 2022) is *"based on a literature analysis of recent scholarship in CLS as published in a wide range of relevant journals [...] and conference*

1 <https://clsinfra.io/about/> (last accessed 2022-06-03)

2 Throughout this document, a differentiation is made between the "inventory" as a list of corpora manually collected and presented in this deliverable and the "catalogue" as the application to explore this dataset.

3 CLS INFRA grant agreement, annex 1 (part A), p. 26

proceedings [...] in order to identify the tools, processes, methods, annotation layers, data and metadata formats and standards used most prominently in the CLS community."⁴ The resulting comprehensive overview of tools, methods and formats employed in the field is valuable input for D6.1 and WP6 in general. Especially the information about formats in which existing data is available in, represents an important input for the technical work packages and is to be compiled into a transformation matrix.

Furthermore, there is a particularly strong connection to and collaboration with WP5, especially for task and deliverable 5.1 "Review of the data landscape," which "*focuses on intellectual access, i.e. providing guidance for finding and sharing literary data*". (Mrugalski et al., 2022).

While WP 5 offers the conceptual foundation guiding the development of the data model, WP 7 and 8 need primarily technical description of the existing data. There is a reciprocal relationship between the work in the WPs 6, 7 and 8: WP6 compiles information about formats, schemas and the structure of the documents in available corpora in general. This is needed by the tool providers in WP8 to match against the formats and structures the tools expect as input and can provide as output. Equally, this information represents input for the definition of the API and the design of the distributed ecosystem of tools to be developed in WP7 ("Building the ecosystem of and for Programmable Corpora"). At the same time WP6, in order to compile the transformation matrix and later to develop the transformation toolbox, also needs to gather information about the input and output formats of the tools which are to form part of the CLS infrastructure.

Deliverable 6.1 is structured as follows: Chapter 3 describes the background and the methodological approach; chapter 4 offers an initial overview of existing data sets and available metadata on corpora. Chapter 5 deals with the data model and the underlying conceptual considerations, chapter 6 details the current status in the development of the transformation matrix, and chapter 7 describes the system design and technical implementation of the catalogue. Finally, the report offers conclusions and an outlook on future tasks (chapter 8). The main body of data, i.e., the information about the corpora collected until now, can be found in the appendix (chapter 10).

3. Background & Methodological approach

Researchers in the area of computational literary studies are confronted with a heterogeneous landscape of existing data and resources, which differ greatly with respect to corpus design and underlying concepts, such as:

- the understanding of the basic concept "text", e.g., as source, edition, data set
- purpose, e.g., general, reference or monitoring corpora, special purpose corpora
- sampling, balancing, representativeness
- annotation model(s)
- data format(s)

⁴ CLS INFRA grant agreement, annex 1 (part A), p. 15

To support the overall goal of the project, i.e. offering a coherent infrastructure that enables the systematic use of digital methods in research work with literary corpora, this task aims to harmonise and consolidate information in the form of (meta)data about the corpora, aiming to answer the question: How can we enable literary scholars to search for and find existing data that are relevant to their research questions?

The challenge of this task is increased by the fact that there is no discipline-wide agreed-upon nomenclature, classification, let alone ontology to describe literary data, with competing schools of thought putting forward differing, potentially contradicting, conceptualisations and a broad spectrum of aspects usable and used as descriptive dimensions. While D5.1 (Mrugalski et al., 2022) offers an in-depth analysis of these varying conceptualisations and typologies used in the field, this task, building on the findings of D5.1, aims for a pragmatic approach, with the primary focus on usability of the inventory/catalogue for potential users, by offering descriptions and criteria maximising the findability and discoverability of literary corpora. Where possible this can also mean accommodating the plurality of approaches in the formalised descriptions and catalogue implementation, i.e., by employing multiple classifications.

As stated in the introduction, the deliverable D3.1 "Baseline Methodological user needs analysis" (Schöch et al., 2022) explored the practice in the field of CLS by examining scholarly articles and extracting information about the methods, tools and formats used in research. Unfortunately, the deliverable does not identify the concrete corpora referred to in the articles, which leaves the analysis on a rather abstract level. Nevertheless, the extracted information on formats, tools and methods (Fileva et al., 2022) may serve as a starting point in the discussion of common vocabularies.

Task 6.1 can roughly be divided into four interrelated subtasks (further detailed in the corresponding subsequent chapters):

- Manual collection of information about existing literary corpora (chapter 4)
- Definition of a conceptual model for describing the data: the so called "CLSCor" data model (chapter 5)
- Automatic generation of data (chapter 6)
- Implementation of the catalogue/exploration platform (chapter 7)

As a starting point and basis for further discussions, metadata about existing literary corpora was manually collected in a spreadsheet document. The collection covers corpora listed in the grant agreement and examples received from the projects partners on request in order to maximise the coverage.

The CLSCor data model serving as conceptual backbone for the work in task 6.1 is based on the Metamodel for Corpus Metadata (MKM) (Odebrecht, 2018), as well as the set of [CIDOC CRM](https://www.cidoc-crm.org/)⁵ ontologies well established and widely used in the field of DH. Especially the extensions [FRBROO](https://cidoc-crm.org/frbroo/)⁶ for describing

5 <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

6 <https://cidoc-crm.org/frbroo/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

bibliographic records and [CRMdig](#)⁷ for describing digital objects, will serve as a solid basis for the conceptual modelling.

The model is formalised as RDF/OWL ontology, accompanied by a semi-structured documentation, so called "recipes", explicating the main entities and the structure of the accompanying information. These recipes, written in Markdown and maintained in a git repository, follow the best practice as developed over the years by the teams using CIDOC CRM and its derivatives and employed in projects, such as [SARI](#)⁸ or the [Census Data Model Documentation](#)⁹. This kind of documentation method serves to understand how the description of different kinds of entities should be expressed in the model.

Wherever possible, structured data on the level of individual documents will be collected and converted with a set of custom scripts into RDF format according to the data model to further populate the dataset with more detailed information, and thus to allow a more fine-grained exploration of the corpora.

Finally, the user-facing catalogue itself will build on the previous steps, by implementing the data model, and ingesting and making available the manually and automatically collected data through an exploratory user interface. Relying on RDF and LOD paradigm, the persistence layer is implemented as a triplestore, the frontend is an instance of an [ResearchSpace](#)¹⁰ system connecting to the triplestore through a SPARQL-endpoint.

4. Initial overview of existing data sets and available metadata on corpora

4.1 General approach

To gain a first, but sufficiently broad basis for devising the data model and as initial input for the catalogue, information on literary corpora was manually collected in a spreadsheet (henceforth referred to as "corpusTable" in this document, attached as appendix), with among other the following attributes (represented as columns in the table): name, acronym¹¹, language, temporal coverage, format, licence and pointers to the corpus or any other related resources. The table was initially populated with the 22 sources listing corpora listed in the grant agreement¹² and continuously expanded through input from project partners and results derived through internet search, employing search terms such as "Corpus linguistics", "TEI XML drama corpora", "TEI annotated language corpora", "literary corpora", and so forth.

7 <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmdig/home-2> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

8 <https://docs.swissartresearch.net/> (last accessed 2022-07-05)

9 <https://census-antiquity-renaissance.github.io/census-csdm/> (last accessed 2022-07-05)

10 <https://researchspace.org/> (last accessed 2022-07-05)

11 In preparation for mapping and ingesting the metadata collected in the corpusTable into the ResearchSpace instance, artificial acronyms had to be created for those corpora which did not provide one, since the acronym will be part of the persistent identifier.

12 CLS INFRA grant agreement, annex 1 (part B), p. 11-12. These corpora are marked blue in the corpusTable (see chapter 10, Annexes)

The compilation of the data was a laborious/time-consuming task: Each corpus website (see column "corpusLink") had to be examined manually for the relevant information. Additionally, in some cases other sources of information on the individual corpora, e.g., reviews (links collected in the column "corpusReview"), secondary pages or supporting GitHub repositories ("additionalLink") were consulted. Given that this information is mostly available in unstructured, verbose form, a major challenge has been to harmonise and consolidate it in line with the preliminary data structure represented by the columns of the table. In many cases, no values (marked with "NaN" in the corpusTable) for certain fields could be provided, because the data was either not available (e.g., in most cases links to APIs or counting words/tokens inside a corpus), or not applicable. The field "additionalInfo / commentary" as well as the commentary function was used to add more detailed information provided by websites, keep track of ambiguous information (e.g., the grant agreement states that the [German Drama Corpus](#)¹³ contains texts from the 1730s-1940s while on the homepage it says 1650s-1940s) and record observations made by the editors of the table.

The goal of this manual curation was not to list all available corpora, but rather to cover as many different formats, languages, annotations, genres, and corpus types as possible and serve as an initial orientation on the level of the corpora. More precise metadata and information will be obtained further into the project by focusing on the individual documents within the corpora. Nevertheless, this initial assortment of corpora provides a very good insight into the challenges and problems of this heterogeneous data collection. It is also worth mentioning that this compilation of corpora is an ongoing task both during the project and beyond.

When compiling an inventory or catalogue, the question of its potential scope is central/crucial. The genre scope might seem defined by the term "literary", however, this term does not draw as sharp of a boundary as could be wished for¹⁴. On the one hand, there is textual material, e.g., in the feuilleton parts of newspapers that potentially qualifies as literary. On the other hand, on the methodological level many of the analytical methods are comparative in nature and require or profit from a baseline, or a reference, e.g., one can only derive the features specific to literary texts by comparing them to non-literary texts. Thus, in the initial phase the focus is on what might be considered as the core of the landscape of literary corpora. Once this baseline is established in the course of the project, the fringes and neighbouring areas should be explored as well.

Given the heterogeneity of the source information, the consolidation and harmonisation of the collected metadata was another major challenge, bearing with it the need for interpretative intervention and potential information loss. At the same time, harmonisation is indispensable to allow systematic discovery.

To account for this, i.e., to preserve as much as possible of the original information to ensure transparency and reproducibility of the curation process, while at the same time allowing for harmonisation in order to make the metadata searchable, the CLSCor data model (described in more detail in chapter 5) needs to allow the distinction of three kinds of information:

13 <https://dracor.org/ger> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

14 A more detailed discussion on the term "literary" can be found in D5.1 (Mrugalski et al., 2022, chapter 3.1)

- a) information provided by the project's or corpus' website or metadata,
- b) information derived from actual data, i.e., the documents inside the corpus, and
- c) the curated, harmonised information.

The following section elaborates on certain aspects encountered during the inventorisation effort, with a focus on challenges for the collection or representation of the relevant information.

4.1.1 Corpus Websites / Provision of (meta)data

Some of these challenges already start with the websites through which corpora are published. The concepts and the approaches applied vary greatly, due on the one hand to the rapid technical development (some websites date back to the early 2000s and even further back, some have technical problems or seem unmaintained), and on the other hand to methodological advances regarding provision of data, most notably the FAIR data principles¹⁵. A crucial aspect in following the FAIR principles as well as for the goals of the CLS project is the availability of the corpus raw data and their metadata in structured formats recognised by the community. Also, in this respect, multiple distinct setups can be encountered, because not all the websites offer the corpora (or metadata) for download and if they do, the data is available in a broad variety of formats. The following setups regarding the provision of corpus (meta)data were observed:

- Provision of only simple (meta)data (differing greatly in format)
- Provision via a web user interface in the form of a presentation-only digital edition, not exposing the underlying raw data (e.g., <http://www.annotating-literature.org/annotations/>)
- websites offering just one corpus as opposed to websites with multiple corpora usable individually or in combination (e.g., DraCor¹⁶, ELTeC¹⁷)
- some of the newer websites offer a variety of corpus exploration tools to access their corpora and provide downloads of the corpora (and their metadata) in different formats. In some cases, these are even accessible via an API (listed under the table heading "corpusAPI"). Some best practice examples are [DraCor](#)¹⁸, [ELTeC](#)¹⁹, [Folger Shakespeare Library](#)²⁰, [LINHD](#)²¹, [Deutsches Textarchiv](#)²², and [Laudatio Repository](#)²³. ELTeC, additionally provides their [schema](#)²⁴ to validate texts against.

In addition, there are websites that serve as portals, i.e., they collect links of other websites which present individual corpora. Some examples are:

15 <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/> (last accessed 2022-07-25)

16 <https://dracor.org/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

17 <https://github.com/COST-ELTeC> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

18 <https://dracor.org/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

19 <https://github.com/COST-ELTeC> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

20 <https://shakespeare.folger.edu/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

21 <https://github.com/linhd-postdata> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

22 <https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

23 <https://www.laudatio-repository.org/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

24 <https://github.com/COST-ELTeC/Schemas> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

- list of most widely used online corpora in English:
<https://www.english-corpora.org/>
- list of Italian corpora:
<https://accademiadellacrusca.it/it/contenuti/banche-dati-corpora-e-archivi-testuali/6228>
- list of corpora provided by CLARIN:
<https://www.clarin-d.net/de/sprachressourcen-und-dienste/korpora>
- list of corpora provided by the University of Essex:
https://www1.essex.ac.uk/linguistics/external/clmt/w3c/corpus_ling/content/corpora/list/index2.html
- Corpus Resource Database (CoRD):
<https://varieng.helsinki.fi/CoRD/corpora/index.html>
- Wikipedia overview of corpora:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_text_corpora
- forText collection of corpora:
<https://fortext.net/ressourcen/textsammlungen>

Here the topicality/up-to-dateness of the provided information is questionable - is the portal still maintained and are all links still working? The examination of all available links found in the different portals, the consolidation and deduplication of the data and creating entries for each corpus in the corpusTable are ongoing tasks.

The language in which the web pages were written posed another problem: Not all websites are written in English or provide an English translation. This makes it difficult to navigate around the site and find the appropriate (meta)data. In order to gather some basic metadata, translation programs were employed as a first step and the sought-after information had then to be extracted from translated descriptions.

4.1.2 Categorisation of corpora, literary genres and timespans

Next to the variety of ways in which corpora are made available, there exist different ways to categorise the corpora themselves. A prominent example is the "typology of corpora according to their purpose" discussed in D5.1, which distinguishes general-purpose collections, reference corpora (subcorpora of), digital critical editions, monitor corpora, corpora compiled on the basis of a research question and opportunistic corpora (Mrugalski et al., 2022, chapter 4.1). This categorisation was also applied in the corpusTable. In addition, for those 22 sources from the grant agreement, the original categorisation into "TEI-Encoded Corpora of Novels", "TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora", "TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora" and "Multi-genre repositories with TEI-encoded texts" was retained (column "classificationCLSProposal"). The decision whether this categorisation/systematisation should be extended onto the other corpora listed in the corpusTable is still pending.

The problems of variety in classifications/distinctions also arise in the case of literary genres and time spans – topics which will be more thoroughly discussed in chapter 5 (subsection "Conceptual modelling considerations"). For the corpusTable the approach was to include original information provided by the

websites (in some cases of literary genres even in the original language) as well as use generally applicable terms (e.g., drama, plays, prose, and fiction for literary genres). For those corpora where information was only available in the original language, the help of literary scholars will be necessary to provide the correct translations for the genre terms, complicated by the fact that traditions of national literatures vary greatly. For information concerning time, a system has to be introduced to represent information like "early modern era, age of Scientific Revolution" or "Middle Ages to the 20th century" in numbers.

4.1.3 Documenting format/schema and annotation

The documentation of formats/schemas as well as annotations used by the corpora represents an important basis for the work on the transformation matrix (chapter 6) and subsequent processing within the infrastructure. In case of the formats, it was possible to consolidate and harmonise most of the data collected. Nevertheless, in order to provide a distinction between metadata formats (providing information about a corpus) and the data formats in which corpora are provided/available for download, a closer inspection of the individual documents inside a corpus is required. Consistent with the analyses of D3.1, the TEI (P4 and P5) and TXT (plain text) formats are, at first glance, among the most frequently used. Additionally, files are also often available in JSON and CSV, as well as in custom-made formats such as [CorA-XML](#)²⁵ (e.g. used by the [Laudatio Repository](#)²⁶).

5. Data model

The conceptual considerations and the development of a data model underlying the catalogue of literary corpora is one of the central tasks in this work package. The data model will allow to express the detailed metadata on literary corpora in a structured manner, thus paving the way for their ingest into the dynamic catalogue, which implements the data model and will enable users to explore the composite dataset.

An embarkation point for the CLSCor data model was the "Metamodel for Corpus Metadata" (MKM) (Odebrecht, 2018), which features the main entities *corpus*, *document* and *annotation* (albeit with a different focus regarding the class annotation, further detailed later in the chapter). Formally, the data model is based on the [CIDOC CRM](#)²⁷ and its related extensions [FRBROO](#)²⁸ for describing bibliographic records and [CRMdig](#)²⁹ for describing digital objects. The data model is still in development; the initial draft of the RDF formalisation is available in the appendix. This chapter provides a description of the current state of the development: After introducing some general modelling and documentation principles, including use of vocabularies in the data model, the modelling considerations for individual aspects will be discussed.

25 <https://cora.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

26 <https://www.laudatio-repository.org/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

27 <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

28 <https://cidoc-crm.org/frbroo/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

29 <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmdig/home-2> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

5.1 Basic modelling principles

The CLSCor data model is formalised in RDF schema as an extension of the base CIDOC CRM schema and some of its extensions, either introducing new classes as specialisations (subclasses) of the base schema, or making direct use of selected classes and properties.

Table 1: Namespaces and URI-schemas used in the data model and the project instance data

Prefix	Namespace/URI-schema	Purpose
crmcls	https://clscor.io/ontologies/CRMcls/	Main CLSCor ontology, extension of CIDOC CRM
crm	http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/	Basic CIDOC CRM ontology
frbr	https://cidoc-crm.org/frbroo/	CIDOC CRM compatible ontology for bibliographic information
crmdig	https://cidoc-crm.org/crmdig/	CIDOC CRM compatible ontology to encode methods of production of digital objects
clst	https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/{vocab-key}/{term-key}	Namespace for defining types
clscore	https://core.clscor.io/entity/{entity-type}/{hash-id}	Dedicated namespace for general, i.e., not corpus-specific instances
{corpus-key}	https://{corpus-key}.clscor.io/entity/{entity-type}/{hash-id} (named graph: https://{corpus-key}.clscor.io/graph) Example: https://textgrid.clscor.io/entity/corpus/xkcd67	Dedicated namespaces for instances from individual corpora. These will be grouped in a corresponding named graph.

Following best practice, entity identifiers shall be generated using a "hash" of some signifier string of the entity (like the corpus name). Thus, the URI for a corpus will be constructed as:

```
https://{corpus-key}.clscor.io/entity/corpus/{shorthash(corpusName)}
```

5.2 Classes and properties

The formal definition of classes and properties will be formulated in an RDF schema (see chapter 10 Annexes for a current draft of the schema). In addition, here is a brief account of the main classes and properties introduced as well as those reused from underlying ontologies:

Main classes:

- **crmcls:X1_Corpus** - subclass of `crm:E73_Information_Object`
- **crmcls:X2_CorpusDocument** - subclass of `crm:E73_Information_Object`
- **crmcls:X3_Feature** - subclass of `crm:E73_Information_Object`

- **crmcls:X4_Project** - subclass of **crm:E7_Activity**

Auxiliary classes:

- **crm:E39_Actor**
- **crm:E56_Language**
- **crm:E55_Type, skos:Concept**

Main properties:

- **crmcls:Y1_has_subcorpus** subproperty of **crm:P148i_is_component_of**
- **crmcls:Y2_documents_should_have_language**
- **crmcls:Y3_documents_should_cover**
- **crmcls:Y4_documents_should_have_type**
- **crmcls:Y5_documents_should_have_feature**

The properties Y2 to Y5 were introduced to allow to express uncertainty when capturing certain characteristics of a corpus based on some second-hand evidence, e.g., description on a corpus website. The semantics of these properties is inspired by the property from FRBRoo model: **frbr:CLR5_should_carry**.

5.3 Vocabularies

The model provides means for expressing various classifiers for describing the objects of interest in a structured manner, i.e., along multiple classifications schemes.

The default CIDOC CRM mechanism for typing will be employed:

```
crm:E1_CRM_Entity - crm:P2_has_type -> crm:E55_Type
```

Additionally, the SKOS schema will be used to construct the vocabularies (instances of **skos:ConceptScheme**). Thus, every concept will be of **crm:E55_Type** and **skos:Concept** with SKOS properties to express semantic relations between concepts (broader, narrower).

Example:

```
<https://clscor.io/type/literaryGenre/poem> a cidoc:E55_Type, skos:Concept;
  skos:prefLabel "Gedicht"@de, "Poem"@en ;
  cidoc:P2_has_type <https://clscor.io/entity/type/literaryGenre>.
<https://clscor.io/type/literaryGenre> a skos:ConceptScheme;
  skos:hasTopConcept <https://clscor.io/type/literaryGenre/poem>.
```

Table 2: Main vocabularies to be used in the data model

Name	Values (initial set)	Description
corpusType	monolingual / comparable / parallel written / spoken / internet language synchronic / diachronic (monitor) general / specialised author's reference / representative (balanced)	Convey the purpose and/or design principle of a corpus. based on the classification used by Czech National Corpus
Language	https://vocabs.dariah.eu/iso639_3/en/	Language tags based on ISO-639-3
literaryGenre	epic / drama / lyric	Basic genre distinction, see section on Literary Genre below
appellationType	fullTitle / acronym	Qualify different appellation of a corpus
linkType	project-website / info-website / review exploration-ui / data-repository / api	Qualify a link

5.4 Modelling documentation - "Recipes"

However, even though an OWL document strictly defines the classes and properties, it is not ideal for practical use, because individual pieces of information are quite atomised and the actual usage patterns are not obvious. Therefore, following best practice, the data model is accompanied by so-called recipes, i.e., a set of semi-structured human-readable documents organised around the main entities, with corresponding properties aligned accordingly, and can be also supported by practical examples. Such documentation should help to understand the practical use of the model, and how the description of different kinds of entities should be expressed in the model.

The original inspiration for the *CLSCor Modelling Recipes* comes from the SARI documentation and the [Census Data Model Documentation](#)³⁰. In these approaches, the notion of "fields" is being used to identify and describe the atomic units of information to be collected and expressed for individual entities. These "fields" can be considered synonymous with attributes, relations or properties in the various formalisations. A crucial contribution of the recipes is the mapping between the fields as understood by the domain experts or users, including a human-readable definition and their actual implementation/expression in the RDF model, described in the form of an RDF-path, as illustrated in the example in Table 3. Thus, the overall structure of the recipes follows the domain conceptualisations, allowing a domain expert to find their way intuitively: individual pages represent the main entities and are further subdivided into logical groupings of specific aspects like naming, classification, existence, parthood or composition. For CLSCor data model this entails the following (preliminary) structure:

³⁰ <https://census-antiquity-renaissance.github.io/census-csdm/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

- Corpus
 - Names
 - Classifications
 - Contributors
 - Parthood
- Corpus document
 - Contributors
 - Format, Schema, Features
- Actors
 - Names and identifiers
 - as contributors to corpus or document (in a specific role)

Table 3: Sample entry for a field definition in the recipes

Field ID	Name	Description	Data Type	RDF Path
f_x	Consists of	Corpus Documents which constitute a Corpus	crmcls:X2	--> crm:P148 --> crmcls:X2

5.5 Conceptual modelling considerations

In the following part, the individual aspects of the underlying data and design considerations regarding their representation in the data model are discussed.

5.5.1 Corpus / Document / Source

The two obvious main entities for the CLSCor data model are corpus and document, corpus being a collection of documents, and document representing a constituent textual unit within the corpus, typically being a representation of a literary work. The model explicitly distinguishes between the document in the corpus and its source. The source would be a certain edition of a printed book; the document an abstract entity acting as a container to various available representations with structural and semantic annotations. If needed the "source"-relation can be extended to also describe translations and other derivative works. These entities have a number of attributes relevant for their description and consequent discovery. While most of the characteristics of the corpus are derived from the characteristics of its constituent documents (e.g. language), the corresponding data point may be available only on the level of corpus, only on the level of individual documents, or on both levels, and it may even be contradictory. The data model thus has to allow for capturing the information on both levels, also expressing its uncertainty. To account for this, a set of properties is introduced which conveys the tentative nature of the information, e.g., `crmcls:Y2_documents_should_have_language` to assert that documents in a corpus are expected to be in a given language, based on some secondary information (e.g. from the website of the corpus). Furthermore, given the variety and potentially open dynamic list of attributes, a generic mechanism to express these features is needed without requiring the adaptation of the data model every time. More details on this mechanism are provided in the section "Annotation, Features & Methods" below.

5.5.2 Literary Genre

The task of finding a suitable systematisation for literary genres is a very difficult one: As stated in the introduction of this deliverable, a variety of schools of thought exist in parallel and potentially contradict each other within the CLS community. As it is not possible to pick one on neutral grounds, the model and approach has to allow for this plurality of positions/perspectives/interpretations.

Thus, to avoid loss of information and a coerced harmonisation, in line with the general approach for the CLSCor data model, the original genre specification as stated on the website of each/every respective research project will be captured using the property `crmc1s:Y4_documents_should_have_type`, indicating that "Documents of corpus X should be of literary genre 'drama'" (recorded in the corpus-specific named graph). In addition, there will also be a default overlay classification, relying on the basic distinction between **epic, drama and lyric**, which can be employed by a non-expert user, while the original categorisation will be available for validation/transparency.

While it is technically possible to apply multiple, potentially even conflicting, classifications and use them in the discovery, such a feature dramatically increases the required curation effort, as well as the cognitive load for the user and are therefore to be avoided.

5.5.3 Corpus Type

While, as with genre, there is no single authoritative corpus typology, some kind of distinction between the different kinds of corpora is needed, not only to make them findable, but also in respect to their reusability and interoperability: Different types of corpora mean different emphases in relation to the research questions, different weighting in omitting/incorporating information, different forms of annotation, etc. - these are important pieces of information, which will also influence the choice of tools which can be applied to these corpora.

D5.1 proposes a primary typology based on the purpose of the corpus (Mrugalski et al., 2022, chapter 4.1):

- General-purpose collections,
- reference-corpora (subcorpora of),
- digital critical editions,
- monitor corpora,
- corpora compiled on the basis of a research question and
- opportunistic corpora.

It further elaborates on "key considerations for selection and sampling (relative to different types of corpora, e.g., exploratory or modelling)" (Mrugalski et al., 2022, chapter 4.2), which are:

- Corpus Architecture / Composition (size, eligibility, structuring of texts and annotations, entity typing)
- Completeness
- Representativeness

- Proportion (Balance)
- Biases

Nevertheless, there is a multitude of possible approaches to categorisation. To give one example, the [Czech National Corpus](#)³¹ is using the following pragmatic classification:

- monolingual / comparable / parallel
- written / spoken / internet language
- prose / poetry / drama
- synchronic / diachronic (monitor)
- general / specialised
- author
- representative (balanced)

Strictly speaking, the distinction between prose/poetry/drama belongs to the literary genre classification, but this example demonstrates very well that the distinction between type and genre is often blurred in practice. For the purposes of the CLSCor data model, we propose to restrict the corpusType to aspects which apply only on the corpus level (due to its compositional nature) and are not applicable/valid for individual constituents/documents.

5.5.4 Language

For standardisation in the area of languages, the use of ISO codes lends itself as best-practice. Nevertheless, and especially in the field of linguistic research, the possibility exists that for example in the cases of extinct languages, special dialects, regional variants or minority languages no ISO codes are provided yet. For those special cases a placeholder/replacement code will have to be generated, to assign a normalised identifier to this language. Additionally, a free text description of the language could be added (under the condition that the provenance of this information is indicated). Earlier considerations trying to match on the best fit within the ISO codes or use another controlled vocabulary instead of ISO codes were not implemented.

Another problem poses the designation "multilingual" in the descriptions of larger corpora covering texts from different languages. This designation is too general/inaccurate and not suitable when searching for corpora which contain a specific language – all corpora with the general description "multilingual" would fall through the search grid. For the catalogue the designation "multilingual" will have to be resolved, listing all available languages contained in the respective corpus.

5.5.5 Format / Schema

The identification of formats and schemas the corpora are available in is crucial for the goal of establishing a consolidated infrastructure, which will allow the application of different tools to the heterogeneous

31 <https://korpus.cz/clarin> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

data. At the same time this is conceptually and technically a highly challenging task, the main obstacle being the availability of sufficiently detailed and reliable information. To explicate: A first approximation to a format is the file ending, or the media-type information. However, neither of these two may be available. Furthermore, even if it is available, it is insufficient - identifying a TEI file as an XML document does not allow it to use its TEI-specific features. To get to the next level, i.e., identifying the inner structure of a document or at least the schema it adheres to, requires inspection of the content, which is not always possible, and always very laborious. In the optimal case, the document refers to the schema it adheres to and can be validated against; however, this basically applies only to XML-based documents. Moreover, with schema-level information there is still the drawback of revealing only what is possible or allowed, and not what information actually is available on the instance level. To access this information, an in-depth analysis of the documents is required, precondition to which is the availability of the raw data. Thus, when describing the format or inner data structure of a corpus and/or its documents, one is confronted with multi-layered information, which is, unfortunately, in most cases not available in full detail. These inner-document structures are only made explicit in the form of format-specific annotations, which will be covered in the next section.

A more detailed analysis of the formats and the more fine-grained inner-document structures, as well as of the ways to consistently describe these both on the side of the data and on the side of the processing tools can be found in chapter 6 Transformation Matrix.

5.5.6 Annotation, Features & Methods

Beyond the indication of format or schema, more fine-grained information about specific features a document (or, more generally, a digital object) exhibits is needed, to understand its inner structure, and to allow assessing the suitability for particular re-use. Structured, reliable and consistent information is essential, especially when further automatically processing the data.

Typical examples of such features are lemmatisation or PoS-tags, but it could be any semantic or structural aspects, like paragraphs, utterances, verses, person names, references etc. These features are encoded in the various formats as some form of annotations or markup.

It is important to highlight the ambiguity of the term "annotation". It can signify both the method (e.g., named entity recognition), the specific activity of applying this method (identifying named entities in a set of documents, e.g., the diaries of Arthur Schnitzler), or the result of this activity, i.e., a specific feature encoded in a document (e.g., all mentions of persons in the document set encoded in TEI annotated with `<persName>` tags).

To avoid confusion regarding the semantics, the data model explicitly introduces the entity Feature (as opposed to Annotation), as a generic mechanism to capture any (structural or semantic) characteristic of a document or text made explicit. e.g., "Text X is annotated with PoS tags".

In this regard, the approach of the CLSCor data model differs from the MKM. In MKM, the class Annotation serves to describe the corresponding annotation process yielding a specific annotation, i.e., considered roughly as a specialisation of an activity. This approach allows to capture the provenance and production of a dataset in minute detail, but only when such corresponding detailed information is available. In the

situation of a catalogue aiming to consolidate existing dispersed and heterogeneous information, corresponding level of detail is seldom available, as witnessed by the survey/overview on literary corpora. Furthermore, as outlined above, it must be possible to distinguish between information on corpus and on document level. That is, there may be information about, e.g., corpus size on the corpus website, next to information generated by inspecting the raw data of the corpus.

As proposed above, the "annotation" information or "information about the features" also serves as a connection point to NLP tools or any other automated processing. In order to enable matchmaking between data and tools, it requires a harmonised, consolidated vocabulary or nomenclature to describe this information, taking into account the complex relation between formats, schemas, features, methods and tools. A more detailed discussion on this topic is in chapter 6 Transformation Matrix.

5.5.7 Timespan / Time issues / Temporal coverage

Information on time and its modelling is a much-discussed and highly complex problem, not only in the field of CLS.

Firstly, there are potentially multiple different dates associated with a literary text: The creation date of the source (which sometimes is difficult to set precisely, e.g. when the creation time spanned over a few decades), the date of the debut performance of a play, publication dates of various editions of a book, the era the author was actively producing literary texts, etc., let alone the question of temporal coverage, i.e. the time in which the content of the work is set. While these distinctions are important for the research process, the corresponding information is often not easily available in a corpus. Besides, accommodating finer distinctions in the system and the data model, as well as the user interface, makes it more complex, thus raising the cognitive load and impairing the ease of use for the user.

Additionally, there is the challenge of corpus vs. document-level information. That is, how to aggregate the information about, for example, the publication date of the works inside a corpus without misleading the user on the actual temporal coverage of the corpus; or how many works published between 1801 and 1900 must a corpus contain to be justifiably labelled a 19th-century corpus of German novels, or whatever assertion it might be.

Finally, there is the demand for structuring this kind of data in terms of literary movements (e.g., Futurism, Postcolonialism, Romanticism, etc.), time periods, or other systematics, which will lay an interpretative filter over the data that can only be understood by someone proficient in this area of systematisation. Furthermore, there are inconsistencies or additional complexities, such as geographic differences (i.e., American vs. British literary periods), no common agreement amongst scholars and scientists on the beginning and end of time periods as well as no parallel development with epochs in other fields, such as architecture, art, music, etc. Such conflicting categorisations are not usable for harmonisation of heterogeneous data in a catalogue. However, they could still be considered as an optional, potentially user-specific overlay, thus forming part of an additional interpretative enrichment.

At the current stage, no final decision has been made with respect to modelling of time, but the general approach is to be as transparent as possible, i.e., to allow the user to reproduce any information which has been introduced in the curation process.

Being an extension of CIDOC CRM – event-based modelling paradigm requires to express all time-related information in terms of events, i.e., one cannot assign a work the attribute "created" with the date as its value, but rather one has to define an instance of a creation event in which the author participated, and of which the work was the output. While this is conceptually a very sound approach, it is tedious in implementation and use of the model.

5.5.8 Person / Role / Organisation / Project

In connection to literary texts and corpora there are persons who have various designations/responsibilities/roles: authors, publishers of the text/corpus, authors of prefaces and/or introductions, people to whom a work is dedicated, editors of the text/corpus, annotators, and researchers, the latter groups often working at different institutions and projects, based at different organisations. Nonetheless, knowledge about these real-world entities constitutes an important meta-information about literary works and corpora.

From these to be strictly differentiated are fictional characters and roles (e.g., in theatrical plays) in the literary works themselves. In practice, there may be overlaps, when, for example, fictional characters which are based on real/historic persons appear in literary texts. Nevertheless, the distinction can and must be preserved, by using distinct relations, i.e., "contributor" versus "features". From the data model point of view, the (explicitly annotated) figures or occurrences of "real" persons in texts would qualify as features, as introduced above.

5.5.9 Licences / Accessibility / Availability

In the discussion around openness and reusability of data³², the information on copyright and/or licensing is of great importance. In the initial list of corpora (corpusTable) as well as the data model, the existence of licences and copyright information is recorded, where available. However, oftentimes the information about the provenance of the data, copyright, and conditions for reuse is missing. For further details, see also section 4.5 of deliverable D5.1 on Access to Corpus Data (Mrugalski et al., 2022, chapter 4.5).

6. Transformation Matrix

One of the goals of task 6.1 is to compile a so-called transformation matrix. This is meant as a systematic overview of formats the corpus data is available in, laid out against the formats the tools to become part of the infrastructure accept as input, or produce as output, indicating potential/needed transformation paths. This overview shall serve as input for task 6.2, which is to deliver a transformation toolbox (D6.2, month 48), a set of scripts or tools allowing to transform data between formats.

A major challenge in this endeavour is the fact that general information about the **format** of a file will normally **not** be **sufficient** to establish the match between data and tools. While there are tools that can perform a general operation, e.g., on any TEI or XML file, many more specialised tools require specific

³² For more insight into this topic, please see D5.1, (Mrugalski et al., 2022, chapter 5 "Legal and Ethical Considerations")

features to be present in the data to operate on. For example, most NLP tools require the texts to be tokenised, lemmatisation is a precondition to part of speech tagging (even if most tools perform these two tasks jointly) and PoS-tags are needed for syntactic parsing. Also, network analysis of speakers in a drama requires the speakers to be explicitly annotated in the text. Therefore, a more fine-grained distinction recognizing specific atomic features of a digitally encoded text is needed, be they structural (e.g., acts or speakers in a dramatic work), linguistic (e.g., lemmas, PoS-tags, morphological information), semantic (e.g., named entities, including persons and places), textgenetical / text-critical or intertextual features.

Standards like **TEI allow for flexibility** in their application, encouraging the users to define bespoke schemas, prescribing a custom structure in a modular way as required for the specific use case. The framework even provides a mechanism to define and describe these customisations, the ODD³³ format, from which established schema formats like XSD or RELAX NG can be derived. This high degree of flexibility, needed and valued in scientific projects, makes the automatic processing and harmonisation of data and metadata more challenging, potentially requiring project- or dataset-specific adaptations to any processing, especially transformation paths. This task is further complicated by the fact that not all projects sufficiently document their considerations - edition guidelines and ODDs/schemas are not always made publicly available.

Moreover, schemas only define which features are allowed in principle, which the documents (as instances of these schemas) may or may not exhibit. Therefore, in order to gain reliable information about the actual inner structure of the documents in a corpus, the actual document content has to be inspected/analysed. Given that this is usually a time-consuming effort, it should ideally be done once and outcomes captured in a summary in the metadata describing the given object. One aspect to take into account is the distinction between the content and its metadata and the corresponding formats. Some formats include metadata as part of the content files, most notably the infamous `<teiHeader>` in the TEI files. In addition, there are a number of dedicated metadata formats (dublincore, CMDI, METS/MODS, MARC, CIDOC/FRBRoo, BIBFRAME etc.). Making data collections and sources in a distributed/scattered/dispersed environment findable through a unified discovery mechanism (catalogue) will require a harmonisation of this heterogeneous metadata. From the transformation matrix point of view there is no principal distinction between content and metadata, e.g., extraction of metadata from a (TEI) document into the CLSCor format is considered just another transformation, as is TEI to plain text.

To allow to systematically capture and to automatically process information about formats and features, and thus to enable matchmaking between data and tools, a **harmonised, consolidated vocabulary or nomenclature** to describe this information is required, taking into account the complex relations between formats, schemas, features, methods and tools. Moreover, such a nomenclature would need to be applied on all involved resources, and thus adopted by all participating parties, that is ideally both the tool and data providers. However, given that we in general cannot expect cooperation from third parties, the corpus metadata will be harmonised on the level of the catalogue curation.

In search for a vocabulary systemizing types/practices/methods of annotation (e.g., part of speech tagging), the Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities (TaDiRAH)³³ can serve as a starting point, however it is both too broad (aiming to cover all research activities) and too shallow (not specific enough about the various NLP/Annotation methods). Also, referring to the ambiguity discussion of the term "annotation", it describes the "activities following some method", not the features resulting from that activity. In general, information about the activities performed is insufficient to enable automated matching. Asserting that PoS-tagging has been performed on a given document, is not sufficient to assume that it can be further processed by a syntactic parser, requiring additional information about the tagset applied.

Other sources to inform this consolidation process include the D3.1 exploring community practices with respect to tools, methods and formats based on an analysis of relevant scholarly articles and the D8.1 "Report of the tools for the basic NLP tasks in the CLS context" (M24).

Central to the development of the infrastructure is the alignment between the data and tool side as dealt with by WP6 and WP7/WP8, respectively. More specifically, on the technical side this means alignment of the development of the distributed ecosystem for Programmable Corpora in WP7 with the transformation matrix as an integral part of the catalogue developed by WP6.

At the core of WP7 is a set of APIs allowing harmonised, yet multifaceted access to data, which will enable the realisation of a FAIR data environment for CLS as a distributed ecosystem of so-called "Programmable Corpora". The details of the architecture are still being worked out (D7.1 M24), but it seems obvious that the catalogue should become the exploration window into the distributed infrastructure. At the same time, the APIs are meant to deliver not just the original raw full text data, but also auxiliary resources, derived from the original input documents, like the social network in a drama, or various precalculated metrics. This effort/goal matches perfectly with the above reasoning for the need of a more fine-grained first-hand analysis of the characteristics, or "Features", of a set of documents. All this prompts the need to tighter integration of the components of the architecture along the same metadata format or model. The concept of "Programmable Corpora" aims at an integration and federation ecosystem based on the ingest of corpora encoded in TEI. However, the inventory of the landscape has revealed that data is oftentimes available in other formats. Here, the transformation matrix and later transformation toolbox will be used for homogenisation.

Thus, taken together, the compilation of the transformation matrix depends on a detailed inspection on the side of the data and on a consolidation on the side of the tools. Given that both these tasks are still in progress, at the current point only a general outline of the matrix can be provided and will need to be refined, as the required information will become available. Nevertheless, important preparatory work can already be performed, namely the consolidation and harmonisation of the terminology between the data and tools part for the different dimensions. In practice, format, schema, individual features, as well as methods are intricately intertwined. As an example: if one wishes to apply the *method* part of speech tagging with *tool* A on a set of documents from *corpus* C, the tool must support the *format* of the corpus documents. Furthermore, depending on the tool, the document must feature explicitly annotated tokens,

33 <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/> (last accessed 2022-07-11)

a result of the method tokenisation. On the other hand, in *tool B*, the tokenisation may be already included as part of the internal NLP pipeline, however it may expect a different format on the side of the input. An explicit goal of the transformation matrix is to identify transformation paths, i.e., transformation steps needed to allow the matching between as many corpora and as many tools as possible. This will serve as input for the transformation toolbox to be developed in T6.2.

Given its widespread use in the field of CLS and DH in general, TEI is considered a lingua franca within the project, i.e., the primary format to work with and to be used for interchange with corresponding transformation paths for data in other formats. The transformation matrix is to become part of the discovery application, or catalogue as outlined further below (chapter 7). The main constituent dimensions of the transformation matrix, together with their corresponding sources, are as follows:

- format (corpusTable, D3.1, D5.1)
- method (D3.1, TaDiRAH)
- tools (D3.1, WP8)

Table 4 compares the formats mentioned in the literature as compiled in D3.1³⁴ and formats of the corpora collected in the inventorisation effort. While TEI (P4 and P5) is the most common format (over 40 corpora are using TEI), corpora/documents are also available in TXT (plain text format; 17 corpora are using the plain text format), PDF (9 corpora), JSON, CSV as well as custom-made formats such as CorA-XML³³.

Table 4: Comparison of formats occurring in corpusTable and D3.1

corpusTable and D3.1	CSV, docx, EPUB, HTML, JPEG, JSON, PDF, SGML, TEI, TEI-P4, TEI-P5, txt, XML, XML RDF
only in corpusTable	Alto XML, CorA-XML, DOC, ELAN, IIIF, JPG, LaTeX, MARC21, MOBI, TCP (TEI P4) XML, XSL_FO, ZIP
only in D3.1	3D Max, 3ds, accdb, ADex, aiff, ArcheoML, ASCII, asf, AVI, bak, bmf, CAD, CARARE, CEI, cgm, CIDOC CRM, dae, db, DB, dBase, DBF, DCMI, DDI, dmp, dng, DTD, Dublin Core, dwf, dwg, dxf, EAD, EDM, EpiDoc, eps, ESRI, exif, fbx, flac, fmp12, fp5, FP7, FRBR, geoTIFF, GIF, indd, iptc-naa, JPEG2000, Keyhole Mark-up Language, LIDO, maff, Manuscriptum XML, MapInfo Interchange, matroska, mbwf, mdb, MEI, METS, mhtml, MIDAS, MIDI, mj2, mkv, MODS, mov, MP3, mp4, mpeg, mpeg-2, MPEG-7, MS Access, MuseData, MusicXML, mxf, MXML, NISO, nxs, oai_dc, odb, ods, odt, ogg, pdf/a, ply, PNG, prc, PREMIS, rf64, RTF, siard, siard2, SkP, SQL, sql Dumb (<i>sic!</i>), stl, SVG, sxc, sxw, TeX, TIFF, TSV, u3d, UTF-8, VRML, W3C Prov, WARC, wav, webCGM, wma, wmv, X3D, XHTML, xls, xlsx, xmp, xsd

34 The data used in Table 4 originates from the csv files, provided by Fileva, et al., 2022 ([results formats full.csv](#))

Based on the above dimensions, the following is a tentative sketch of the transformation matrix structures with mock data for illustration purposes:

Information about a corpus – in which format is it available and which features does it exhibit (if available, information about the tools used to generate those features).

Table 5: Information about a corpus

Corpus	Corpus document format	Feature	Method	Tool
corpus1	TEI	tokens	tokenisation	
		lemmas	lemmatisation	my_lemmatiser
		PoS-Tag	PoS-tagging	tree-tagger
corpus2	TEI			

Information about a tool – which format and features does it expect as input and produce as output.

Table 6: Information about a tool

Tool	Method	input Format	input Feature	output Format	output Feature
tree-tagger	PoS-Tagging	verticale	token	verticale	token, lemma, PoS-tag
OxGarage		TEI		PDF	
		DOCX		TEI	
		[...]		[...]	

Transformation paths – identify the sequence of processing steps for given input, desired processing method and desired output.

Table 7: Transformation paths

Path	available input Format	available input Feature	desired output Format	desired output Feature	Method
1	TEI		TEI	PoS-tag	PoS-Tagging
2	CSV	speakers	graphML	character-network	Network Analysis
3	[...]	[...]	[...]	[...]	[...]

The general procedure for the use of the transformation matrix is the following:

- there is a dataset D available in format S with featureset F

- researcher wants to analyse/annotate/enrich this data according to method M, producing a new feature f_{new} integrated in a new version of the dataset (D_{enriched}) in same format S
- there is a tool T implementing method M, requiring (and delivering) format S'
- following transformation path (with transformations T_x) is needed:
 - $D(S,F) \xrightarrow{T_x(S,S')} D'(S',F) \Rightarrow T(D'(S',F)) \Rightarrow D_{\text{enriched}}(S, F+f_{\text{new}})$

Exemplified with a concrete example: Applying PoS-Tagging on a (untokenised) TEI document:

- Input format: TEI document
- Select a tool for method PoS-Tagging: tree-tagger
- tree-tagger only accepts `verticale` (tokenised plain text) on input
- a transformation is required and performed from TEI to `verticale`
- Apply tree-tagger on the transformed data, creating yet another new version of the document
- The user wants to continue working on a TEI document, prompting another transformation from `verticale` to TEI, ideally this transformation should retain all potential original annotation i.e., merging the original TEI with the new feature PoS-tag.

There are some open technical issues to be considered:

- **Lossy transformations:** Many NLP tools expect plain text as input. Assuming TEI as the default format within the infrastructure, i.e., the primary format to work with and to be used for interchange, the seemingly rather trivial default transformation path would be TEI to plain text. However, with the additional requirement that the added features should be integrated into the original TEI, the whole transformation mechanism needs to be adjusted, amounting to merging two documents or digital objects along a defined key, which in the case of plain text can only be byte-offset or the token sequence.
- **Storage for derivatives:** when new versions of documents or derivatives are being created, where should these be stored? The user will typically want to download them and work locally. Furthermore, in general the data does not belong to the provider of the input documents. At the same time, in the interest of re-use, this enriched dataset should be made available, ideally within the infrastructure (i.e., via the catalogue), in order to allow its recursive use and reuse.
- **Feedback into catalogue:** When data is being processed, the output should ideally be automatically equipped with metadata and registered in the catalogue.

7. System design & Technical implementation

The main goal of T6.1 is "to build an inventory to capture the heterogeneous landscape of data sources and available formats defined by WP5 in relation to the tools and services in the ecosystem to process these."

Already at the beginning of building the inventory of corpora for CLS, it was clear that a simple spreadsheet would not meet the needs of the potential users nor the technological ambition within the project – it was and is the vision of this work package to create a corpus exploration platform, where users can search for and explore corpora. The platform should contain details about the individual corpora, but also provide features such as a typed/indexed search and statistics on the main entities (e.g., corpus, documents inside a corpus, language, format/schema, annotation, etc.). Another desiderata was to create a "living" catalogue, which allows metadata interconnection/-linking and enrichment with other resources. The concept of publishing the inventory as linked open data in the form of a knowledge graph, lends itself to fulfilling these requirements.

Though the inventory initially is a manually collected and curated dataset with information on the level of corpora, eventually this is going to be moulded into a dynamic system - a catalogue or discovery solution, allowing querying and browsing the dataset.

Some basic characteristics of this system will be:

- Implementation of the CLSCor data model
- Triplestore as underlying persistence, implying also a SPARQL endpoint
- User interface for querying and browsing
- Possibility to ingest further information (enrichment)

7.1 Metadata collection & transformation, and catalogue population

To populate the catalogue and ingest the collected information on literary corpora into the system, the data has to be structured in RDF according to the data model. Given the heterogeneity of the information, a source-specific transformation step is required. For the purpose of these transformations a set of python notebooks, which are ideally suited to analyse and convert this heterogeneous data, has been developed. These notebooks are maintained in the project's dedicated [GitLab instance](#)³⁵.

Once the data has been transformed into RDF, it will be ingested into the triplestore, from where it will be available through the web user interface, as well as the SPARQL endpoint. The catalogue population is an iterative process, given that many issues with data representation only become visible once displayed and explored in the catalogue. In a backtracing process, it needs to be determined whether the problems are on the presentation side, stem from the transformation step, or are inherited from the original data. Correspondingly, adjustments need to be done in the customisation of frontend, or in the transformation scripts, followed by another ingestion.

To allow for repeated ingestion of individual datasets and a systematic management of the data in the catalogue in general, individual ingestions are grouped in dedicated named graphs. Currently, next to the corpusTable, initial mapping on the level of documents has been implemented also for the corpora TextGrid and Laudatio/REM. Moreover, an RDF representation of the data from D3.1 about user needs analysis has been proposed and ingested to the catalogue. It is yet to be determined in how far this "secondary" information can be squared/aligned with the information about the corpora.

³⁵ <https://gitlab.clsinfra.io/cls-infra/wp5wp6> (last accessed 2022-07-11) currently access is restricted to project members

7.2 Catalogue

The web application serving as catalogue is an instance of the open-source knowledge management system *ResearchSpace*³⁶, developed by the British Museum and used by many projects in the domain of digital humanities and cultural heritage.

ResearchSpace offers a coherent set of UX components, which let the user "create, manipulate, analyse and visualise data that can be searched contextually and continually expanded by new knowledge."³⁷ Next to the simple keyword search there is the so-called query-builder, a UX-component that guides the user through formulating more complex queries by offering relevant categories and relations between them to pick from. It allows rendering the results according to custom templates in a variety of forms or visualisations (grid, table, charts, map, timeline, etc.) as well as to save them to a clipboard and / or download them as structured data. Relying on a linked open data representation of the data modelled in RDF as dynamic knowledge graph stored in one or multiple triplestores, these components can be parametrised and populated with data using standard SPARQL queries.

More details on the functionality and customisation options of *ResearchSpace* can be found in its documentation as well as in the deliverable D6.4 of the PARTHENOS project (Bardi, 2019).

Building on this powerful system, the CLSCor catalogue is envisaged to provide four main features or functionalities:

- Browse through (knowledge) graph
- Typed/indexed Search
- Statistics
- Details about individual corpora

These features translate into four main parts implemented as a project-specific customisation of *ResearchSpace*:

- **Starting page and main navigation pages**
main entry point, offering primary structure of and navigation through the dataspace
- **Search**
simple keyword search supported by faceting, as well as more complex search allowing to query individual attributes or relations between entities with custom display of results
- **Statistics**
tables and charts with statistics about various aspects of the data space
- **Detail view**
pages displaying information about individual entity - its properties and relations to other entities

36 <https://researchspace.org/> (last accessed 2022-06-03)

37 <https://researchspace.org/semantic-tools/> (last accessed 2022-06-03)

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

Following are a few illustrative screenshots from the catalogue prototype:

The screenshot shows the 'DraCor' research space interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home / DraCor' on the left and an 'Edit Page' link on the right. Below this is the 'DraCor' logo and the text 'DraCor Research Space'. A horizontal menu contains 'Overview', 'Corpora', 'Authors', 'Plays' (which is highlighted with a blue underline), and 'Characters'. Below the menu is a search bar labeled 'Filter Results' with a magnifying glass icon. The main content area is titled 'play' and lists ten plays by Goethe and Josef Alois Gleich, each on a separate line with a horizontal separator below it. The plays listed are: 'Gleich, Josef Alois: Der Eheteufel auf Reisen. Lokales Zauberspiel mit Gesang in zwei Aufzügen', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Clavigo. Ein Trauerspiel', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Das Jahrmarktsfest zu Plundersweilern. Ein Schönbartspiel', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Der Bürgergeneral. Ein Lustspiel in einem Aufzuge', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Der Großkophta. Ein Lustspiel in fünf Aufzügen', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Der Triumph der Empfindsamkeit. Eine dramatische Grille', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Des Epimenides Erwachen. Ein Festspiel', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Die Laune des Verliebten. Ein Schäferspiel in Versen und einem Akte', 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Die Mitschuldigen. Ein Lustspiel in einem Akte', and 'Goethe, Johann Wolfgang: Die natürliche Tochter. Trauerspiel'. At the bottom right of the list, there is a pagination control showing a series of numbers from 1 to 11, with the number 1 highlighted in a dark blue box.

Figure 1: Overview page of a DraCor corpus with listing of the plays contained in the corpus

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

Figure 2: Detail view for the corpus “Folger Shakespeare Library” and selected related entities visualised as knowledge graph

Figure 3: Detail view for the corpus “TextGrid: Digitale Bibliothek” and selected related entities visualized as knowledge graph

8. Conclusions & Outlook

This deliverable offers a discussion of the heterogeneous landscape of literary corpora, highlighting their wide variety with respect to structure, context and purpose, and the differing modes of provisioning. It also points out the various challenges WP 6 has been confronted with in the effort to collect information about these resources and consolidate it into a structured form. The most frequent ones are inconsistency, vagueness, or lack of information.

While in this initial phase, the data was compiled manually in a spreadsheet and only on the level of corpora, the ultimate goal is to develop and provide a dynamic discovery solution, a catalogue which allows the users to explore the structured and elaborate data. Though the original project's grant agreement did not specify the nature of the inventory or catalogue, it became clear during the initial curation process that a dynamic technical solution is required to allow capturing the complexity and dynamics of the information, and allow for exploration and use by human users as well as applications.

The conceptual base for such a catalogue is a data model allowing to express the required breadth and depth of information, the salient aspects of which have been outlined in this deliverable, as have been the technical considerations on the system design. Here, the major challenge is to express the vagueness and uncertainty of the data both in the model as well as in the application. At the same time, harmonisation of the heterogeneous information against well-defined controlled vocabularies is a precondition to allow systematic discovery, i.e. making the resources findable. A LOD-based technology stack has been proposed and is being developed, relying on the open source framework *ResearchSpace*.

While the deliverable already offers a comprehensive insight into the landscape, the collected information remains largely on the level of corpora. To arrive at detailed information about the formats and features of the datasets, an in-depth analysis of individual corpora on the level of its constituent documents is required, which will be an ongoing action point in task 6.1 for the remainder of the project.

A crucial outcome of task 6.1 is to be a transformation matrix, a systematic overview of formats the corpus data is available in and formats supported by the tools, serving as an interoperability hub between data and tools. Owing to this component relying on detailed information both from in-depth analysis of the corpora and of the tools to become part of the infrastructure, only its preliminary outline can be provided at this point in the project.

Finally, next to the core goal of the task to allow the exploration of the literary corpora landscape, the current findings suggest a number of potential future avenues to pursue:

- Ensure long-term availability of technically outdated but potentially valuable material
- Work on harmonising and improving overall quality of metadata in the field
- Support data providers in their effort to make datasets available by offering advice and consultation, best practices, guidelines, workshops or tools)

9. References

- Bardi, Alessia / Bruseker, George / Durco, Matej / Illmayer, Klaus / Broeder, Daan / Lorenzini, Matteo / Resch, Stefan / Sugimoto, Go / Theodoridou, Maria / Assante, Massimiliano (2019): "PARTHENOS D6.4 Report on services and tools (final)", Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2607212>
- Fileva, Evgenia / Dudar, Julia / Schöch, Christof (2022): "Supplementary data to the Baseline Methodological User Needs Analysis [Data set]. In Baseline Methodological User Needs Analysis (v1.1.0)", Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6325465>
- Mrugalski, Michał / Odebrecht, Carolin / Charvat, Vera / Börner, Ingo / Ďurčo, Matej (2022): "CLS INFRA D5.1. Review of the Data Landscape", Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6861022>
- Odebrecht, Carolin (2018): "MKM – ein Metamodell für Korpusmetadaten. Dokumentation und Wiederverwendung historischer Korpora", Dissertation. Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Sprach- und literaturwissenschaftliche Fakultät, Berlin. <https://doi.org/10.18452/19407>
- Schöch, Christof / Fileva, Evgeniia / Dudar, Julia (2022): "CLS INFRA D3.1 Baseline Methodological User Needs Analysis", Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6389333>

10. Annexes

10.1 Data Model (first draft)

These two appended .ttl files were taken from the CLS Infra GitLab instance³⁸ which is currently only available for project internals.

[crmcls_ontology.ttl](#)³⁹

```
@prefix crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/> .
@prefix crmcls: <https://clscor.io/ontologies/CRMcls/> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
```

```
crmcls:X1_Corpus a rdfs:Class ;
  rdfs:label "Korpus"@de,
  "Corpus"@en ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E73_Information_Object .
```

```
crmcls:X2_Corpus_Document a rdfs:Class ;
  rdfs:label "Korpus-Dokument"@de,
```

38 <https://gitlab.clsinfra.io/cls-infra/wp5wp6/mkm-cidoc/-/tree/main/model/export> (last accessed 2022-07-13)

39 https://gitlab.clsinfra.io/cls-infra/wp5wp6/mkm-cidoc/-/blob/main/model/export/crmcls_ontology.ttl (last accessed 2022-07-13)

```

    "Corpus Document"@en ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E33_Linguistic_Object,
    crm:E73_Information_Object .

crmcls:X3_Project a rdfs:Class ;
    rdfs:label "(Forschungs-)Projekt"@de,
    "(Research) Project"@en ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E7_Activity.

crmcls:Y1_has_subcorpus a rdf:Property ;
    rdfs:label "hat als Subkorporus"@de,
    "has subcorpus"@en ;
    rdfs:comment "associates a corpus with its subcorpus"@en ;
    rdfs:domain crmcls:X1_Corpus ;
    rdfs:range crmcls:X1_Corpus ;
    rdfs:subPropertyOf crm:P148_has_component .

crmcls:Y1i_is_subcorpus_of a rdf:Property ;
    rdfs:label "ist Subkorporus von"@de,
    "is subcorpus of"@en ;
    rdfs:comment "associates subcorpus with its super corpus"@en ;
    rdfs:domain crmcls:X1_Corpus ;
    rdfs:range crmcls:X1_Corpus ;
    rdfs:subPropertyOf crm:P148i_is_component_of .

crmcls:Y2_documents_should_have_language a rdf:Property ;
    rdfs:label "sollte Dokumente in der Sprache enthalten"@de,
    "documents should have language"@en ;
    rdfs:comment "associates a corpus with the language of one or more Corpus
Documents"@en ;
    rdfs:domain crmcls:X1_Corpus ;
    rdfs:range crm:E56_Language .

crmcls:Y2i_should_be_language_of_documents a rdf:Property ;
    rdfs:label "sollte die Sprache von Dokumenten im Korpus sein"@de,
    "should be language of documents in corpus"@en ;
    rdfs:comment "associates a language of one or more Corpus Documents with their
corpus"@en ;
    rdfs:domain crm:E56_Language ;
    rdfs:range crmcls:X1_Corpus .

crmcls:Y3_documents_should_cover a rdf:Property ;
    rdfs:label "Dokumente sollten Zeitspanne abdecken"@de,
    "documents should cover time-span"@en ;
    rdfs:comment "associates a corpus with the time-span covers the datings of the
documents"@en ;
    rdfs:domain crmcls:X1_Corpus ;
    rdfs:range crm:E52_Time-Span .

crmcls:Y3i_should_be_covered_by_documents a rdf:Property ;
    rdfs:label "sollte durch die Dokumente in einem Korpus abgedeckt werden"@de,
    "should be covered by documents in corpus"@en ;

```

```

rdfs:comment "associates a time-span with the corpus presumably containing
documents that cover it"@en ;
rdfs:domain crm:E52_Time-Span ;
rdfs:range crmcls:X1_Corpus .

```

```

crmcls:Y4_documents_should_have_type a rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:label "Dokumente sollten als Typ haben"@de,
    "documents should have type"@en ;
  rdfs:comment "associates a corpus with the type of the documents"@en ;
  rdfs:domain crmcls:X1_Corpus ;
  rdfs:range crm:E55_Type .

```

```

crmcls:Y4i_should_be_type_of_documents a rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:label "sollte der Typ der Dokumente sein"@de,
    "should be type of documents"@en ;
  rdfs:comment "associates type with the corpus that is presumeably the type of one
or more documents"@en ;
  rdfs:domain crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:range crmcls:X1_Corpus .

```

[clscor_types.ttl](#)⁴⁰

```
@prefix crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/> .
```

```
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
```

```

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/corpus-creation> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Erstellung eines Korpus"@de,
    "Creation of a Corpus"@en .

```

```

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/institution> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Institution"@de,
    "institution"@en .

```

```

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/institution/department> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Abteilung"@de,
    "department"@en .

```

```

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/measurement-unit/KB> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Kilobyte [Einheit]"@de,
    "Kilobyte [Unit]"@en .

```

```

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/measurement-unit/document> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Korpus-Dokument [Einheit]"@de,
    "Corpus Document [Unit]"@en .

```

```

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/measurement-unit/token> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Token [Einheit]"@de,
    "Token [Unit]"@en .

```

40 https://gitlab.clsinfra.io/cls-infra/wp5wp6/mkm-cidoc/-/blob/main/model/export/clscor_types.ttl (last accessed 2022-07-13)

```
<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/measurement-value/estimate> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Geschätzter Wert"@de,
        "Estimated value"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/measurement-value/number-of-documents> a
crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Anzahl an Korpus-Dokumenten"@de,
        "Number of corpus documents"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/measurement/estimate> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Schätzung"@de,
        "Estimate"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/measurement/number-of-documents> a crm:E55_Type;
    rdfs:label "Ermittlung der Anzahl an Korpusdokumenten"@de,
        "Getting number of corpus documents"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/name/forename> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Vorname"@de,
        "forename"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/name/full> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Name [Format: Nachname, Vorname]"@de,
        "full name [format: surname, forename]"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/name/surname> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Nachname"@de,
        "surname"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/organisational-subdivision> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Subeinheit einer Organisation"@de,
        "Organisational subdivision"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/textClass> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Texttyp"@de,
        "Type of Text"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/ts/temporalCoverage> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "Zeitliche Abdeckung"@de,
        "Temporal Coverage"@en .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/application/tei+xml> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "TEI-XML"@de,
        "TEI-XML"@en ;
    crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/application/xml> a crm:E55_Type ;
    rdfs:label "XML"@de,
        "XML"@en ;
    crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/text/csv> a crm:E55_Type ;
```

```

    rdfs:label "CSV: kommasseparierte Datendateien"@de,
      "CSV"@en ;
    crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/text/plain> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Plaintext"@en ;
  crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/text/tab-separated-values> a
  crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "TSV: tabulator-separierte Datendateien"@de,
    "TSV"@en ;
  crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/title/acronym> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Akronym"@de,
    "Acronym"@en ;
  crm:P127_has_broader_term <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/title> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/title/full> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Langtitel"@de,
    "Full Title"@en ;
  crm:P127_has_broader_term <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/title> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/annotator> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Annotator/in"@de,
    "Annotator"@en ;
  crm:P127_has_broader_term <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor> ;
  crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor-role> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/editor> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Herausgeber/in"@de,
    "Editor"@en ;
  crm:P127_has_broader_term <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor> ;
  crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor-role> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/title> crm:P127i_has_narrower_term
<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/title/acronym>,
  <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/title/full> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Beteiligte/r"@de,
    "Contributor"@en ;
  crm:P127i_has_narrower_term <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/annotator>,
  <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/editor> ;
  crm:P2_has_type <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor-role> .

<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor-role> a crm:E55_Type ;
  rdfs:label "Typ Beiteilige/r-Rolle"@de,
    "contributor role type"@en ;
  crm:P2i_is_type_of <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/annotator>,
  <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/contributor>,

```

```
<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/editor> .
```

```
<https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type> a crm:E55_Type ;  
  rdfs:label "MIME-Type"@en ;  
  crm:P2i_is_type_of <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-  
  type/application/tei+xml>,  
  <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/application/xml>,  
  <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/text/csv>,  
  <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/text/plain>,  
  <https://core.clscor.io/entity/type/mime-type/text/tab-separated-values> .
```

10.2 corpusTable

Due to the size of the corpusTable, the Excel sheet had to be cropped into 3 parts. The *id* column serves as connection point between the cropped parts.

10.2.1 corpusTable part 1

Table 8: Columns: *id*, *corpusName*, *classificationCLSProposal*, *corpusAcronym*, *corpusLink*, *corpusLanguage*, *corpusTextCount* (=Docs in Corpus), *corpusWordCount* (words in corpus)

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
1	Drama Corpora Project	NaN	DraCor	https://dracor.org/	Alsatian, Bashkir, French, German, Greek, Italian, Roman, Russian, Spanish, Swedish, Tatar	NaN	NaN
2	Alsatian Drama Corpus	NaN	AlsDraCor	https://dracor.org/als	Alsatian	25	NaN
3	Bashkir Drama Corpus	NaN	BashDraCor	https://dracor.org/bash	Bashkir	3	NaN
4	Calderón corpus	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	CalDraCor	https://dracor.org/cal	Spanish	201	NaN
5	French Drama Corpus	NaN	FreDraCor	https://dracor.org/fre	French	1560	NaN
6	German Drama Corpus	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	GerDraCor	https://dracor.org/ger	German	569	NaN

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id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
7	German Shakespeare Drama Corpus	NaN	GershDraCor	https://dracor.org/gersh	German	37	NaN
8	Greek Drama Corpus	NaN	GreekDraCor	https://dracor.org/greek	Greek	39	NaN
9	Italian Drama Corpus	NaN	ItaDraCor	https://dracor.org/ita	Italian	139	NaN
10	Roman Drama Corpus	NaN	RomDraCor	https://dracor.org/rom	Latin	36	NaN
11	Russian Drama Corpus	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	RusDraCor	https://dracor.org/rus	Russian	212	NaN
12	Shakespeare Drama Corpus	NaN	ShakeDraCor	https://dracor.org/shake	English	37	NaN
13	Spanish Drama Corpus	NaN	SpanDraCor	https://dracor.org/span	Spanish	25	NaN
14	Swedish Drama Corpus	NaN	SweDraCor	https://dracor.org/swe	Swedish	68	NaN
15	Tatar Drama Corpus	NaN	TatDraCor	https://dracor.org/tat	Tatar	3	NaN
16	Reference corpus Middle High German	NaN	ReM	https://doi.org/10.34644/laudatio-dev-xCS3CnMB7CArCQ9C3LRB	Diachronic German	396	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
17	Deutsches Textarchiv	Multi-genre repositories with TEI-encoded texts	DTA	https://www.deutschtextarchiv.de/	German	4448	NaN
18	Folger Shakespeare Library	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	FolgerShake	https://shakespeare.folger.edu/	English	37	NaN
19	Anemoskala: Corpus of Modern Greek Poetry	TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora	Anemoskala	http://www.greek-language.gr/digitalResources/literature/tools/concordance/index.html	Greek	NaN	NaN
20	Wikisource	NaN	Wikisource	https://wikisource.org/wiki/Wikisource:TEI	NaN	NaN	NaN
21	European Literary Text Collection	TEI-Encoded Corpora of Novels	ELTeC	https://github.com/COST-ELTeC	NaN	2500	NaN
22	1000 Novel Corpus	NaN	1000Novel	http://hdl.handle.net/11321/312	Polish	1000	NaN
23	Annotating Literatures	NaN	AnnotLit	https://www.annotating-literature.org/	English	NaN	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
24	The CLiGS textbox	NaN	CLiGS	https://github.com/cligs/textbox	French, Spanish	NaN	NaN
25	Perseus digital library	NaN	Perseus	http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/collections	Greek, Roman, Arabic	NaN	NaN
26	Reference corpus Altdeutsch	NaN	DiaGer	https://doi.org/10.34644/laudatio-dev-WiWkDnMB7CArCQ9CyBEw	Diachronic German	129	650000
27	Stanford Literary Lab	NaN	StanfordLitLab	https://litlab.stanford.edu/	NaN	NaN	NaN
28	Théâtre Classique	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	TheaClass	http://www.theatre-classique.fr/pages/programmes/PageEdition.php	French	1620	12980645
29	Shakespeare His Contemporaries	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	SHC	https://github.com/JonathanReeve/corpus-SHC	NaN	509	NaN
30	Letteratura teatrale nella	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	NaN	http://www.letteraturaitaliana.net/aut	Italian	139	NaN

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
	Biblioteca italiana			ori/carlo_goldoni.html			
31	Dramawebben	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	DramaWebben	https://litteraturbanken.se/dramawebben	Swedish, Latin, French, German, English	8234	394190260
32	Ludvig Holbergs skrifter	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	LHS	http://holbergsskrifter.dk/holberg-public/view?docId=adm/main.xml	Danish, Latin	86	NaN
33	Biblioteca Electrónica Textual del Teatro en Español de 1868–1936	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	BETTE	https://github.com/HDAUNIR/BETTE	Spanish	25	NaN
34	Emothe: The Classics of Early Modern European Theatre	TEI-Encoded Drama Corpora	EMOTHE	https://emothe.uv.es/en/	Italian, English, French, Spanish	113	NaN

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
35	British Women Romantic Poets	TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora	BWRP	https://digital.lib.ucdavis.edu/projects/bwrp/	English	NaN	NaN
36	Diachronic Spanish Sonnet Corpus	TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora	DISCO	http://prf1.org/disc-o/	Spanish	4303	NaN
37	Freiburger Anthologie	TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora	FRAN	http://freiburger-anthologie.de/	German	1300	NaN
38	Poetess Archive	TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora	PoetessArchive	https://poetessarchive.org/	English	4000	NaN
39	Russian Poetic Corpus	TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora	RusPoet	https://ruscorpora.ru/new/en/search-poetic.html	Russian	NaN	NaN
40	Corpus Sonetos del Siglo de Oro, ed. Borja Navarro Colorado	TEI-Driven Poetic Corpora	SonetSiglo	https://github.com/bncolorado/CorpusSonetosSigloDeOro	Spanish	5000	NaN
41	TextGrid Repository, including	Multi-genre repositories with	TextGrid	https://textgrid.de/digitale-bibliothek	German	NaN	NaN

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
	“Digitale Bibliothek”	TEI-encoded texts					
42	Biblioteca italiana	Multi-genre repositories with TEI-encoded texts	Bibita	http://www.bibliotecaitaliana.it/	Italian	3523	NaN
43	Oxford Text Archive	Multi-genre repositories with TEI-encoded texts	OTA	https://ota.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/	Algonquin, Amele, Ancient Greek, Anglo-Norman, Arabic, Bengali, Cameroon Pidgin, Classical Syriac, Croatian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, Egypt Sign Language, English, Esperanto, French, Fulah, Galician, German, Guarequena, Gujarati, Hanga, Hebrew, Hindi, Irigwe, Irish, Italian, Japanese, Jur Modo, Kurdish, Latin, Latvian, Malay, Malayalam, Mandarin Chinese, Middle English, Middle French, Middle High German, Middle Irish, Multiple languages,	63854	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
					Nunggubuyu, Official Aramaic, Old English, Old French, Old Frisian, Old High German, Old Norse, Old Provençal, Old Spanish, Orya, Pali, Panjabi, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Romany, Russian, Sanskrit, Scots, Scottish Gaelic, Serbian, Serbo-Croatian, Slovenian, Spanish, Sumerian, Swedish, Tamil, Tibetan, Turkish, Urdu, Welsh		
44	PHI Latin Texts: Classical Latin Texts. A Resource Prepared by The Packard Humanities Institute	NaN	PHI	https://latin.packhum.org/	Latin	NaN	NaN

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
45	Korpus der Literarischen Moderne/Corpus of Literary Modernism	NaN	KOLIMO	https://kolimo.uni-goettingen.de	German	NaN	NaN
46	Deutsches Lyrik Korpus/German Poetry Corpus	NaN	DLK	https://github.com/tnhaider/DLK	German	75141	17335638
47	Scottish Corpus of Texts & Speech	NaN	SCOTS	https://www.scottishcorpus.ac.uk/	Scottish	1316	4587602
48	The Corpus of Modern Scottish Writing	NaN	CMSW	https://www.scottishcorpus.ac.uk/cmsw/	Scottish	356	5434830
49	Corpus Resource Database	NaN	CorD	https://varieng.helsinki.fi/CoRD/corpora/index.html	NaN	NaN	NaN
50	Austrian Books Online	NaN	ABO	https://onb.ac.at/digitaler-	NaN	NaN	NaN

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
				lesesaal/austrian-books-online-abo			
51	1-Satz-Korpus	NaN	1SatzCor	https://github.com/satzomat/corpus	German	NaN	NaN
52	Historisches Textkorpus	NaN	HistCor	https://www.ids-mannheim.de/lexik/abgeschlosseneprojekte/historischeskorpus/	German	NaN	45000000
53	Text Creation Partnership	NaN	TCP	https://textcreationpartnership.org/	English	73000	NaN
54	Project Gutenberg	NaN	PG	https://www.gutenberg.org/	NaN	60000	NaN
55	Project Gutenberg Australia	NaN	PGAus	https://gutenberg.net.au/	English	5000	NaN
56	Projekt Gutenberg-DE	NaN	PGGer	https://www.projekt-gutenberg.org/	Deutsch	10000	NaN
57	txtlab Multilingual Novels	NaN	txtlab	https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/txtlab_Novel450/2062002/3	German, French, English	450	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
58	LINHD POSTDATA Project	NaN	LINDH	https://github.com/linhd-postdata	Spanish, French, German, Italian, Latin, Dutch, Portuguese	NaN	NaN
59	Biblioteka Maksima Moshkova	NaN	LibRu	http://lib.ru/	NaN	NaN	NaN
60	Internet Biblioteka Alekseia Komarova	NaN	ILibRu	https://ilibrary.ru/	NaN	NaN	NaN
61	Ruskaia virtual'naia Biblioteka	NaN	RVB	https://rvb.ru/	NaN	NaN	NaN
62	Fundamental'naia elektronnaia biblioteka „Ruskaia literatura i fol'lor“	NaN	FEB	http://www.feb-web.ru/	NaN	NaN	NaN
63	HathiTrust Digital Library	NaN	HATHI	https://www.hathitrust.org/	NaN	17000000	NaN

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
64	"To be continued . . .": The Australian Newspaper Fiction Database	NaN	TBC	http://cdhrdatasys.anu.edu.au/tobecocontinued	English	21000	NaN
65	Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes	NaN	Cervantes	http://www.cervantesvirtual.com/	Spanish, English	NaN	NaN
66	Europeana	NaN	Europeana	https://www.europeana.eu/de	NaN	22559106	NaN
67	Polona	NaN	Polona	https://polona.pl/	NaN	3667722	NaN
68	Gallica	NaN	Gallica	https://gallica.bnf.fr	French, Spanish, English, German, Portuguese, Latin, Greek, Romanian, Romansh,	9004194	NaN
69	DIKDA - Písomné kultúrne dedičstvo Slovenska	NaN	DIKDA	https://dikda.eu/	NaN	28244	NaN
70	Zlatý Fond SME	NaN	SME	https://zlatyfond.sme.sk/autori#U	Slovak	NaN	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
71	Univerzitná Knižnica v Bratislave	NaN	UKB	http://digitalna.kniznica.info/browse	Slovak, English, German, Arabic, Estonian, French, Russian, Slovene, Turkish	99319	NaN
72	World Digital Library	NaN	WDC	https://www.loc.gov/collections/world-digital-library/about-this-collection/	NaN	18933	NaN
73	Federacja Bibliotek Cyfrowych	NaN	FBC	https://fbc.pionier.net.pl/	Polish, German, Latin, English, French, Russian, Ukrainian, Lesing-Gelimi, Dutch, Czech	8500000	NaN
74	Open Texts	NaN	OpenTexts	https://opentexts.world/	NaN	8000000	NaN
75	Travel writings on Italy	NaN	Travelltal	https://sites.google.com/view/travelwritingsonitaly/home	English	30	NaN
76	Fashist Latin Texts	NaN	FLT	https://flt.hf.uio.no/	Latin	NaN	NaN
77	Musisque Deoque. A digital archive of Latin	NaN	MQDQ	https://www.mqdq.it/public/index	Latin	NaN	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
	poetry, from its origins to the Italian Renaissance						
78	Poeti d'Italia in lingua latina	NaN	PDI	http://mizar.unive.it/poetiditalia/public/	Latin	NaN	NaN
79	Humanist and Renaissance Italian Poetry in Latin	NaN	HIP	https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/collection?collection=Perseus:collection:PDILL	Latin	NaN	2802940
80	NOSCEMUS	NaN	NOSCEMUS	https://wiki.uibk.ac.at/noscemus/Main_Page	Latin	1500	NaN
81	LatTy on Zenodo	NaN	LatTy	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1454630	Latin	90	NaN
82	LatTy under PhiloLogic	NaN	LatTyPhilo	http://solr.ffzg.hr/p_hilo4/latty2/	Latin	NaN	NaN
83	Academia Gustaviana (1632-1656) ladinakeelse	NaN	NeoLat	https://philologic.uu.t.ee/neolatina/	Latin, Greek	NaN	NaN

id	corpusName	classificationCLS Proposal	corpusAcronym	corpusLink	corpusLanguage	corpusText Count (=Docs in Corpus)	corpusWord Count (words in corpus)
	juhuluule tekstikorpus						
84	Thomas More Concordances	NaN	TMC	https://essentialmore.org/concordances/	Latin, English	NaN	NaN
85	Marko Marulić, Judita and Daidias	NaN	MM	https://teipublisher.com/exist/apps/judita-davidias	Latin	2	NaN
86	CAMENA on Zenodo	NaN	CAMENA	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1454036	Latin	1751	50458045

10.2.2 corpusTable part 2

Table 9: Columns: id, corpusTimespan, corpusFormat/Schema, corpusAnnotation, corpusLiteraryGenre, corpusType, corpusAPI

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/ Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
1	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
2	19th and 20th century	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
3	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
4	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
5	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
6	1650s–1940s	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
7	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
8	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
9	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
10	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
11	1740s–1940s	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
12	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
13	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
14	1880–1900	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
15	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://dracor.org/doc/api
16	1050–1350	CorA XML, ANNIS	parts of speech, morphology and lemma	prose, lyric	Reference corpus	https://www.laudatio-repository.org/docs/elasticapi/
17	1500–1900+	TEI	POS, tokenized, lemmatized	NaN	Monitor Corpus	https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/api
18	1564(jul)–1616(greg)	TEI, HTML, DOC, PDF, TXT, XML	NaN	drama	Monitor Corpus	https://shakespeare.folger.edu/the-folger-shakespeare-api/
19	1801–2000	TEI, TXT	NaN	lyric	Monitor Corpus	NaN
20	NaN	PDF, HTML, EPUB	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
21	1840–1920	TEI	NaN	prose, novels	Monitor Corpus	NaN
22	NaN	TXT	NaN	prose, novels	Based on a Research Question	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
23	NaN	NaN	NaN	prose, lyric, fiction	Monitor Corpus	NaN
24	NaN	TEI	NaN	NaN	based on a Research Question	NaN
25	NaN	TXT	NaN	NaN	Digital Critical Edition	NaN
26	750–1050	TEI, ELAN, ANNIS	POS, "Flexionsmorphologie"	prose, lyric	Reference Corpus	https://www.laudatio-repository.org/docs/elasticapi/
27	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
28	1601–1800	TEI	NaN	"Tragédies, Comédies, Proverbes, Tragi-comédies, Monologue, Drame, Saynètes, Opéras, Parodie, Pastorales, Parades"	Monitor Corpus	NaN
29	1550–1660	TEI	[homepage: tokenized, linguistically annotated]	drama	Monitor Corpus	NaN
30	13.Jh-today	[TEI info from proposal]	NaN	[drama, plays]	NaN	NaN
31	1248–today	TEI	[Homepage search lists the following	drama, plays	Monitor Corpus	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
			possibilities: Search for a word or phrase, include conjugation forms, include older spellings, search by word meaning, search for word endings, search by part of speech"]			
32	NaN	TEI	NaN	comedies, historical works, non-fiction/prose, essays, writings related to comedies, autobiography	Monitor Corpus	NaN
33	1868–1936	TEI (P5)	acotaciones, nombre de personajes, lista de personajes, referencias a nombres de personajes (mediante nombre propio) dentro del texto, cursiva, encabezamientos,	drama, plays	Monitor Corpus	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
			paratextos iniciales y finales [translation: annotations, name of characters, list of characters, references to character names (by proper name) within the text, italics, headings, initial and final paratexts]			
34	NaN	TEI	NaN	drama, plays	Monitor Corpus	NaN
35	1789–1832	TEI	NaN	poems	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
36	1401–1900	TEI	NaN	poems, sonnets	Monitor Corpus	NaN
37	1720–1900	TEI	NaN	poems	NaN	NaN
38	1750–1900	TEI	NaN	poems	General-Purpose	NaN
39	NaN	TEI	NaN	poems	Reference Corpus	NaN
40	1500–1700	TEI	metrical patterns	poems, sonnets	Monitor Corpus	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
41	NaN	TEI	NaN	NaN	Monitor Corpus	NaN
42	Middle Ages to the 20th century	TEI	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
43	BCE–present	TEI	NaN	multigenre: novels, plays, poetry	General-Purpose	NaN
44	NaN	NaN	NaN	classical latin texts	General-Purpose	NaN
45	NaN	TEI, TXT	POS	NaN	based on a Research Question	NaN
46	NaN	TEI (P5), JSON	NaN	poems	Monitor Corpus	NaN
47	1945–today	NaN	Homepage "not grammatically annotated. Some mark-up is used in transcriptions of spoken material"	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
48	1700–1945	TXT	NaN	"Administrative prose, expository prose, personal writing, instructional prose, religious prose, verse/drama,	General-Purpose Collection	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
				imaginative prose, journalism, orthoepists"		
49	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	diverse	NaN
50	1880–today	NaN	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
51	NaN	TEI, CSV, TXT	NaN	"Novellen, Romane, Maerchen"	Based on a Research Question	NaN
52	1700–1918	TEI	NaN	"drama, humanities, legal texts, letters, narrative prose, historical newspapers, scientific texts, sermons, fairy tales, sagas, ..."	Reference Corpus	NaN
53	NaN	TCP (TEI P4) XML, SGML, TEI (P5)	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
54	NaN	TXT, HTML, EPUB, MOBI, LaTeX	NaN	"literary works and reference items of historical significance"; also	General-Purpose Collection	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
				audio books,music, pictures		
55	NaN	TXT, HTML, EPUB, MOBI	NaN	NaN	General- Purpose Collection	NaN
56	NaN	TXT, HTML, EPUB, MOBI	NaN	NaN	General- Purpose Collection	NaN
57	1170 –1930	TXT	NaN	novels	Based on a Research Question	NaN
58	NaN	TXT, XML, TEI, HTML	metrics, rhyme, entities	poetry	Monitor Corpus	NaN
59	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	General- Purpose Collection	NaN
60	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	General- Purpose Collection	NaN
61	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	General- Purpose Collection	NaN
62	11th century to 20th century	NaN	NaN	literature, folklore, dictionaries, encyclopedias, Russian scholarship	General- Purpose Collection	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
63	NaN	PDF, EPUB, TXT, ZIP, JPG	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	https://www.hathitrust.org/d ata
64	19th and early 20th century	NaN	NaN	fiction (novels, novellas, short stories)	Monitor Corpus	NaN
65	NaN	EPUB, PDF, MARC21, HTML	NaN	literature, language, history, letters	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
66	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	https://pro.europeana.eu/page/apis
67	NaN	XML RDF, JPEG, PDF, ZIP	NaN	books, periodicals, maps and atlases, ephemera, photographs, prints and drawings, manuscripts, postcards and musical scores	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
68	NaN	TXT, EPUB, XML, PDF, JPEG	NaN	books, manuscripts, images, maps, newspapers, audio, music, video, objects	General-Purpose Collection	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
69	NaN	NaN	NaN	written documents	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
70	800 to present	NaN	NaN	Slovak literature	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
71	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
72	1000-2000	NaN	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
73	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
74	from 15th century onwards	TXT, PDF, Alto XML, IIIF	NaN	NaN	General-Purpose Collection	NaN
75	19.–20. century	TEI, TXT	NaN	"travel writing"	Based on a Research Question	NaN
76	1922–1943	PDF	author, works, themes, inscriptions	poetry, prose	Digital Critical Edition	NaN
77	NaN	NaN	search by lemma, form, metrical scan, co-occurrences,	poetry, prose	Monitor Corpus	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
			metrical typology, distance/order, variants			
78	1250–1550	NaN	word form, metrical scan, distance/order, variants, author, work	poetry	Monitor Corpus	NaN
79	birth of Dante until the first half of the sixteenth century.	XML	NaN	Italian poetry	NaN	NaN
80	early modern era, age of Scientific Revolution	XML, TXT	NaN	selection of early modern works on science written in Latin	NaN	NaN
81	NaN	XML, DOCX	NaN	Tyrolean Neo-Latin texts	Based on a Research Question	NaN
82	Renaissance to present day	NaN	NaN	Neo-Latin texts	Digital Critical Edition	NaN
83	1850–1940	NaN	NaN	Latin and Greek texts	Digital Critical Edition	NaN
84	NaN	NaN	NaN	works of Thomas More	Digital Critical Edition	NaN

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	corpusTimespan	corpusFormat/Schema	corpusAnnotation	corpusLiteraryGenre	corpusType	corpusAPI
85	1450–1524	XML, ePub, PDF, LaTeX, XSL-FO	NaN	works of Marko Marulic (Marcus Marulus)	Digital Critical Edition	NaN
86	early modern Europe	XML	NaN	poetry, historical and political writings, letters, dictionaries, handbooks	Based on a Research Question	NaN

10.2.3 corpusTable part 3

Table 10: Columns: id, websiteStatus, corpusLicence, corpusReview, additionalLink, additionalInfo / commentary, sourceOfInformation

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfInformation
1	online	CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org	Commentary: This is the overall-page starting page with links to the individual drama corpora, which are listed in the following lines of this table (Alsatian, Bashkir, Calderón, French, German, German Shakespeare, Greek, Italian, Roman, Russian, Shakespeare, Spanish, Swedish, Tatar); Dracor provides very sophisticated info, a lot of valuable information can be scraped via the API	Homepage
2	online	CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/alsdracor	NaN	Homepage
3	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage
4	online	CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/caldracor	Proposal: "Calderón corpus (54 plays)"	Proposal, Homepage
5	online	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/fredracor	NaN	Homepage
6	online	CC0	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/gerdracor	Proposal: "German Drama Corpus: 481 German-language plays from 1730s–1940s"	Proposal, Homepage
7	online	CC0	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-	NaN	Homepage

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
				org/gershdrac or		
8	online	CC BY-SA 3.0 US	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/greekdracor	NaN	Homepage
9	online	CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/itdracor	NaN	Homepage
10	online	CC BY-SA 3.0 US	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/romdracor	NaN	Homepage
11	online	CC0	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/rusdracor	Proposal: "Russian Drama Corpus: 210 Russian-language plays from 1740s–1940s"	Proposal, Homepage
12	online	CC BY-NC 3.0	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-org/shakedracor	Homepage: "derived from the Folger Shakespeare Library"	Homepage
13	online	CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)	NaN	NaN	Homepage: "Forked from the BETTE corpus (Biblioteca Electrónica Textual del Teatro en Español de 1868–1936)."	Homepage
14	online	CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)	NaN	https://github.com/dracor-	Homepage: "Derived from the eDrama (https://litteraturbanken.se/dramawebben/sida/edrama) project"	Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfInformation
				org/swedracor		
15	online	CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0)	NaN	NaN	Homepage: "provided through Tatar Electronic Library."	Homepage
16	online	CC BY-SA 4.0	NaN	NaN	<p>Commentary: The laudatio repository uses a custom XML (CorA XML) and custom linguistic search and visualization tool (ANNIS); the ReM is only one of the corpora provided by the laudatio repository</p> <p>Homepage: "The "Reference Corpus of Middle High German" (short: ReM) is a corpus of diplomatically transcribed and annotated texts from Middle High German (1050-1350) with a size of around 2 million word forms. It originated from the research projects "Reference Corpus of Middle High German" and "Middle High German grammar". Texts have been digitized and richly annotated, e.g. with parts of speech, morphology and lemma"</p>	Homepage, personal information from Carolin Odebrecht
17	online	CC BY-NC 3.0	https://ride.iid.de/issues/issue-6/deutsches-textarchiv/	NaN	<p>Proposal: "Deutsches Textarchiv, http://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/ (4165 texts, all in TEI)"</p> <p>Commentary: Multi-genre repositories with TEI-encoded texts; consists of a "Kernkorpus" (1468 texts) and additional corpora (5014 texts); metadata available in DC and CMDI; also OAI-PMH; very informative project-website with various features,</p>	Proposal, Homepage

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
					documentation, download-area, etc. (but only available in German)	
18	online	CC BY-SA 4.0	NaN	NaN	Proposal: "Shakespeare Folger Library: all (37) Shakespeare plays, very high encoding-depth " Commentary: corpus of a single author; contained in ShakeDraCor	Proposal, Homepage
19	online	NaN	https://ride.iid-e.de/issues/issue-8/anemoskala/	NaN	Proposal: "Anemoskala: Corpus of Modern Greek Poetry (19th and 20th century) " Review: "publication policy does not allow any kind of download, export or further reuse of any part of the textual corpus"; "plain text, TEI-XML files, metadata, concordance results" Commentary: no download possible; homepage only in Greek	Proposal, Homepage, Review
20	online	GFDL, CC-BY, CC-BY-SA	https://ride.iid-e.de/issues/issue-8/wikisource/	NaN	NaN	Review

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
21	online	NaN	NaN	<p>An overview of the current state in ELTeC corpus building can be found here: https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/</p> <p>Work on the different ELTeC corpora is in progress here: https://github.com/COST-ELTeC</p> <p>A collection of relevant documentation can be found here: https://distantreading.github.io/</p>	<p>Proposal: "One of the aims of the Distant Reading COST Action (2017-2021) is to coordinate the creation of a multilingual European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC). The ELTeC core will ultimately contain at least 10 linguistically annotated subcollections of 100 novels comparable in their internal structure in at least 10 different European languages, totalling at least 1,000 full-text novels from the period 1840-1920. The extended ELTeC will take the total number of full-text novels to at least 2,500. Novels have been chosen among major literary genres for availability and size. Chronological limits are due to constraints related to copyright and availability of quality full texts."</p>	Proposal, Homepage

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
				ELTeC page on Zenodo, with archived releases, one for each corpus: https://zenodo.org/communities/eltec/		
22	online	CC BY-SA 4.0	NaN	NaN	Homepage: "Corpus of literary texts intended as benchmark collection for text categorization. It contains 1000 novels written in polish or translated to polish by various authors. Each text is stored as separate .txt file." Commentary: Download all files: https://clarin-pl.eu/dspace/handle/11321/312?show=full#	Homepage
23	online	NaN	NaN	http://www.annotating-literature.org/annotations/	Commentary: They provide a styleguide for annotating: http://www.annotating-literature.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Styleguide-2020-08-11.pdf	Homepage
24	online	CC BY-SA 4.0	NaN	https://github.com/cligs/toolbox	NaN	Homepage (Github)

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
25	online	NaN	https://ride.iid-e.de/issues/isue-8/perseus/	NaN	NaN	Homepage
26	online	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	NaN	http://www.ddeutschdiachro ndigital.de/	Homepage (DE): "Das Referenzkorpus Altdeutsch erfasst und annotiert die ältesten Sprachdenkmäler des Deutschen vom Beginn der kontinuierlichen schriftlichen Überlieferung um 750 bis etwa 1050 mit einem Umfang von ca. 650 000 Textwörtern. Aufgenommen werden alle in dieser Zeit überlieferten Texte des Althochdeutschen und des Altsächsischen in einer möglichst genauen Wiedergabestufe. Dabei werden die handschriftengetreuesten gedruckten Texteditionen zugrundegelegt. Die Annotation erfasst Header-Informationen, strukturelle (Wort, Satz, Zeile, Absatz etc.) und linguistische Annotationen (Part of Speech-Tagging, Flexionsmorphologie) sowie syntaktische Satzinformationen und erfolgt mit Unterstützung einer semi-automatischen Vorannotation, die mit Hilfe der digitalisierten Sprachstufen- und Textwörterbücher und Glossare zum Althochdeutschen und zum Altsächsischen erzeugt wurde. Die verschiedenen Stufen der Annotation werden in Form einer Mehrebenenarchitektur	Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
					aufeinander bezogen." Commentary: one of the corpora provided by the laudatio repository	
27	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage: "The Stanford Literary Lab is a research collective that applies computational criticism, in all its forms, to the study of literature." Commentary: No texts available, no possibility of download, just textual information about projects	Homepage
28	online	NaN	https://ride.iid-e.de/issues/issue-8/theatre-classique/	<p>statistic on corpus: http://www.theatre-classique.fr/pages/programmes/corpus.php analysis of person/actor in drama: http://www.theatre-classique.fr/pages/PagePersonnages.html</p>	<p>Proposal: "Théâtre Classique: 1.350 plays (from 17th and 18th century)" Commentary: TEI with tei-all invalid, undocumented customizations [M. Goebel set up a pipeline to do a cleaned up ingest into dracor]; from 17th and 18th century; homepage is entirely in French.</p>	Proposal, Homepage, Review, personal information from project teammembers

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
29	online	NaN	NaN	Tool developed by authors of SHC corpus: https://github.com/DH-Box/corpus-downloader	Proposal: "Shakespeare His Contemporaries: 853 plays written between 1550–1700"	Proposal, Homepage
30	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	page in Italian, not very informative	Proposal, Homepage
31	online	NaN	https://ride.iid-e.de/issues/isue-6/litteraturbanken-the-swedish-literature-bank/	about-page: https://litteraturbanken.se/om/english.html (in English)	Proposal: "Dramawebben: 62 Swedish plays" Commentary: It looks as if Dramawebben is only one collection of the "litteraturbanken"; files are available as e-pub; available in SweDraCor	Proposal, Homepage
32	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Proposal: "Ludvig Holbergs skrifter: 36 comedies" Commentary: no info if texts are downloadable, seems you can only look at the texts online, no XML Files available, but there is a doku (in Danish): http://holbergsskrifter.dk/holberg-public/view?docId=adm/userHelp.xml (see "Guidelines for textual encoding")	Proposal, Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
33	online	NaN	NaN	https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/10444419	Proposal: "Biblioteca Electrónica Textual del Teatro en Español de 1868–1936 (BETTE): 25 Spanish plays" Commentary: contained in SpanDraCor; metadata encoded in TEIHeader; VIAF IDs	Proposal, Homepage
34	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Proposal: "Emothe: The Classics of Early Modern European Theatre: 113 plays incl. translations (Italian, English, French, Spanish)" Commentary: certificate on homepage has expired (page not safe?)	Proposal
35	online	NaN	NaN	https://quod.lib.umich.edu/b/bwrp/	Proposal: "British Women Romantic Poets, 1789–1832" Commentary: Currently only an older version is available. On the starting page, a note says "The British Women Romantic Poets archive is being transitioned to a new home. This page will automatically redirect to the new location when it becomes available."; Homepage: "Last content update May 23, 2001."	Proposal, Homepage
36	online	CC-BY licence	NaN	https://github.com/pruizf/disco	Proposal: "DISCO (Diachronic Spanish Sonnet Corpus, over 4,000 sonnets by more than 1,000 authors, incl. canonical as well as non-canonical authors, 15th to the 19th century)" Homepage (about-section: https://prf1.org/disco/about.html): 15th to the 19th century; over 4,000 sonnets by more than 1,000 authors, incl. canonical as well as non-canonical	Proposal, Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
					authors; "The raw texts were in most cases extracted from Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes (1999), with some 18th-century texts coming from Wikisource."	
37	offline	NaN	NaN	NaN	Proposal: "Freiburger Anthologie (1.300 German-language poems from 1720–1900)" Commentary: network timeout; page not reachable	Proposal
38	online	NaN	NaN	Editorial Principles: https://poetesarchive.org/about/principles.html Instructions: https://poetesarchive.org/about/template.html XML-template: https://poetesarchive.org/about/annualtemplate-full.xml	Proposal: "Poetess Archive (flowery poetry written in Britain and America between 1750–1900)" Homepage: "Work Flow: Every bibliographic entry in the Poetess Archive has been made into a TEI-encoded page (see "Editorial Principles" for more about TEI). We have created TEI templates and will continue to create them for those who wish to submit texts already encoded, but we accept submissions of any kind, and then TEI-encode them here. After that work, the TEI pages are: - created into HTML presentation pages; - entered into our Oracle database; - made into RDFs so that the Poetess Archive Database is interoperable with NINES using the NINES COLLEX TOOL."	Proposal, Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
39	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	<p>Proposal: "Russian Poetic Corpus (part of the Russian National Corpus)"</p> <p>Homepage: "The Poetry corpus, which facilitates searches not only by lexical and grammatical features but also by specifically poetical features, such as meter, rhyme types, etc,"</p> <p>related paper: https://wp.hse.ru/data/2018/12/29/1143017363/77LNG2018.pdf</p>	Proposal, Homepage
40	online	CC BY-NC 4.0	https://ride.iid-e.de/issues/is sue-6/corpus-of-spanish-golden-age-sonnets/	http://adso.gpsi.es/index.php/en/corpus-of-metre/	<p>Proposal: "Corpus Sonetos del Siglo de Oro, ed. Borja Navarro Colorado (more than 5000 Spanish sonnets, ca. 1500-1700, with metrical annotation)"</p>	Proposal, Homepage
41	online	CC BY 3.0 DE	NaN	https://gitlab.gwdg.de/dariah-de/textgrid-digitale-bibliothek	<p>Proposal: "Multi-genre repositories with TEI-encoded texts" "TextGrid Repository, including "Digitale Bibliothek" (all texts in TEI)"</p> <p>Homepage: "Literatur, Märchen, Geschichte, Kulturgeschichte, Kunst, Musik, Philosophie, Soziologie, Nachschlagewerke"</p> <p>Commentary: more detailed info might be in the Gitlab-repo</p>	Proposal, Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
42	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	<p>Proposal: "Biblioteca italiana, http://www.bibliotecaitaliana.it/ (3523 texts, many of them in TEI)"</p> <p>Commentary: page only in Italian; focus on Italian literature; 3 collections; info is very well hidden (no direct links, you have to click your way to the relevant information and then translate it); metadata is available in METS, MAG; some files available in TEI P4 (e.g. http://www.bibliotecaitaliana.it/scheda/bibit001300)</p> <p>Homepage (translation from Italian into German with DeepL; http://www.bibliotecaitaliana.it/page/726):</p> <p>"Textkodierung: Bibit hat das Kodierungsschema der Text Encoding Initiative (TEI P4), das auf der Syntax der Extensible Markup Language (XML) basiert, als Textkodierungssprache übernommen. Angesichts der Breite des TEI-Schemas wurden im Rahmen des Bibit-Projekts mehrere Kodierungsebenen festgelegt, denen ein Text unterworfen werden kann. Derzeit sind alle Texte in der digitalen Bibliothek auf den folgenden Kodierungsebenen:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Niveau 1: Strukturelle Gliederungen, ausdrückliche Zitate, Betonungen und Abschnitte in anderen Sprachen als der Basissprache des Textes 	Proposal, Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
					Niveau 2: Strukturelle Gliederungen mit expliziten Typangaben, explizite Zitate, Hervorhebungen, Überschriften von zitierten Texten und Abschnitten in anderen Sprachen als der Basissprache des Textes, einfache redaktionelle Eingriffe"	
43	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	<p>Proposal: "Oxford Text Archive, https://ota.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/ (209 novels, 350 plays, 64 collections of poetry; most in TEI)"</p> <p>Homepage: "A repository of full-text literary and linguistic resources. Thousands of texts in more than 25 languages."; "The Oxford Text Archive (OTA) is a repository of digital literary and linguistic resources for research and teaching. The OTA was created at and remains a part of the University of Oxford. We also offer advice to resource creators about best practice for creating digital resources, and to users of digital resources on how to benefit from existing resources."</p> <p>Commentary: founded by Lou Burnard & Susan Hockey; currently under review (nov2021); they provide single entries in DC, via OAI-PMH, use CMDI, BIBTEX, handles, support open data (but also support restricted access data); clear info on licenses; The OTA is a registered CLARIN C Centre, and the repository is based on the CLARIN DSpace platform; OTA collections can be found via the VLO; records are</p>	Proposal, Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfInformation
					displayed with their metadata and download possibilities (HTML, TEI, epub, ?); advanced search: https://ota.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/repository/xmlui/discovers?advance	
44	online	NaN	https://ride.iid.de/issues/issue-8/phi/	NaN	Review: "Although technologically obsolete by today's standards (e. g. TEI/XML are not used), PHI is still one of the most widely used open access text collections of Roman literature." Homepage: "This website contains essentially all Latin literary texts written before A.D. 200, as well as some texts selected from later antiquity."	Homepage, Review
45	currently offline	NaN	NaN	for examples see derived corpus: https://github.com/ingoboeerner/kolimoschnitzler	Homepage (redirected): "The eXistdb-corpus "KOLIMO" is currently being overhauled for re-launch. It was built at the University of Göttingen 2015-2017."; "KOLIMO allows running quantitative profiles of language use. This means essentially "counting stuff at the language surface". We work with the basic assumption that "style" may be assessed by means of frequency counts of those textual features that are easily distinguishable by the computer: characters, syllables, words, sentences, and so on, combining to measures such as word length, sentence length, type-token ratios, most frequent word lists, etc. Abundant stylometric research shows that this straightforward approach to	Homepage, personal information from Ingo Boerner

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
					<p>style is quite fruitful. Of course, any more advanced analysis may start here, including cluster analysis of text-similarity based on most frequent word counts (e.g., delta), or entropy measures of lexical variation. Anything goes, as long as we have a hold on the discrete enties that make up the texts (characters, strings etc.)."</p> <p>combines texts taken from DTA, Textgrid, Project Gutenberg + Metadata"; "KOLIMO is made available under a Creative Commons license, in line with the licenses of the source repositories. The texts from TextGrid are available under a CC-BY attribution license (see textgrid digitale bibliothek). However, the Deutsches Textarchiv documents are made available under a CC BY-NC 3.0 license (non-commercial, see creative commons), meaning that commercial use of those texts is prohibited (see nutzungsbedigungen dta). Gutenberg-DE documents are made available in a way that we understand as a CC-BY-NC-SA license (non-commercial, share alike, see creative commons), meaning that commercial use of those texts is prohibited, and remixing, transformation, or building upon the material only if using the same license as the original. When using the corpus, please ensure to cite the sources of the texts as required by the distinct statements, and give</p>	

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
					credit to the KOLIMO team listed below, for doing the text compilation, annotation, and working on the metadata"	
46	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: lots of info in the github readme, needs to be filtered; corpus ca be downloaded in .zip files; compiled from Textgrid and DTA; Some digital research on poetry based on this corpus, see https://www.aesthetics.mpg.de/institut/mitarbeiterinnen/thomas-haider.html ; Especially: https://arxiv.org/abs/2102.08858 ; Lines + minimal metadata in a JSON object / python dictionary	Homepage
47	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage: "The Scottish Corpora project has created large electronic corpora of written and spoken texts for the languages of Scotland. The Scottish Corpus of Texts & Speech (SCOTS) has been online since November 2004, and, after a number of updates and additions, has reached a total of nearly 4.6 million words of text, with audio recordings to accompany many of the spoken texts. A sister resource, the Corpus of Modern Scottish Writing, was launched in 2010, and now comprises 5.4 million words of written text with accompanying images."; "Search criteria "General, spoken written" Commentary: They offer an advanced search and some analysis tools:	Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
					https://www.scottishcorpus.ac.uk/advanced-search/ https://www.scottishcorpus.ac.uk/tools/	
48	online	NaN	NaN	download entire corpus as plain text https://www.scottishcorpus.ac.uk/cmsw/download-corpora	Homepage: "The Corpus of Modern Scottish Writing (CMSW) is an electronic corpus of written and printed texts from the period 1700-1945, complementing the Helsinki Corpus of Older Scots (1450-1700) and the Scottish Corpus of Texts & Speech (1945-present day)."; "147,129 total types; 5434830 total tokens"	Homepage
49	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: it is a database/list of corpora; "CoRD provides descriptions of a large number of corpora, subcorpora and databases. Many more are forthcoming and we encourage all compilers of English language corpora to submit a description."	Homepage
50	online	NaN	NaN	https://search.onb.ac.at/prio-explore/search	Homepage (DE): "Im Rahmen einer Public Private Partnership mit Google hat die Österreichische Nationalbibliothek seit 2011 insgesamt rund 600.000 urheberrechtsfreie Werke mit insgesamt 200	Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
				h?query=&tab=onb_fulltext&search_scope=ONB_aleph_abo&vid=ONB	Millionen Seiten digitalisiert, darunter auch jene 200.000 Bücher, die sich im Prunksaal befinden. Damit sind alle digitalisierten Bücher erstmals vollständig und kostenlos zugänglich, können im Volltext durchsucht oder auch als PDF heruntergeladen werden. Diese erfolgreiche Zusammenarbeit mit Google wird nun fortgesetzt: Ab 2019 werden jene Jahrgänge historischer Werke digitalisiert und online gestellt, bei denen mittlerweile das Urheberrecht erloschen ist. Die „moving wall“, bis zu der digitalisiert wird, liegt derzeit beim Erscheinungsjahr 1880 und wird jährlich um ein Jahr verschoben; der große Sicherheitsabstand von 140 Jahren setzt sich aus der urheberrechtlichen Schutzfrist von 70 Jahren nach dem Tod der AutorInnen und 70 Lebensjahren ab Erscheinen ihrer Werke zusammen: Dadurch ist gewährleistet, dass selbst dann kein urheberrechtlich geschütztes Buch digitalisiert wird, wenn die AutorInnen zum Zeitpunkt der Veröffentlichung noch sehr jung waren und lange gelebt haben."	
51	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage
52	online	NaN	NaN	searchable via: https://www2 .ids-	Homepage (DE: "zwei Querschnittskorpora mit Texten der Sach- und Gebrauchsliteratur (z.B. Wörterbuch- und Lexikonartikel, Zeitungen und Zeitschriften, wissenschaftliche Texte, Gesetzestexte)	Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
				mannheim.de /cosmas2/	und drei Korpora mit Textsammlungen aus der Reihe „Digitale Bibliothek“: Deutsche Literatur von Lessing bis Kafka (DB 1), Philosophie von Platon bis Nietzsche (DB 2), Deutsche Literatur von Frauen (DB 45). [...] Teilkorpora die Sagen, Kinder- und Hausmärchen der Brüder Grimm, Goethes Werke und die Marx-Engels-Gesamtausgabe." contains the "GerManC": https://www.ids-mannheim.de/fileadmin/lexik/uwv/dateien/GerManC_Documentation.pdf	
53	online	NaN	NaN	Evans: https://www.dropbox.com/sh/inyy253jvytoxcu/AAAT9nMPo0sa5aXEgs5SC5aGa?dl=0 , EEBO: https://www.dropbox.com/sh/pfx619wnjdck2lj/AAAeQjd_dv29oPymNoKJWfEYa?dl=0 , ECCO: https://www.	Commentary: TCP hosts four collections (Early English Books Online, Navigations, Eighteenth Century Collection, and Evans Early American Imprints); every collection has its own site; Navigations collections also has a Github repository (https://github.com/Text-Creation-Partnership/EEBO-TCP-Collections-Navigations)	Homepage

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
				dropbox.com/sh/inhwjphw682i2gf/AAC8NixNye8Gp0smYBTly2Y9a?dl=0		
54	online	NaN	NaN	machine-readable (offline) catalogue: https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/offline_catalogs.html	NaN	Homepage
55	online	NaN	NaN	Index: https://gutenberg.net.au/gutindex_au.txt	Commentary: no new ebooks are added to the collection	Homepage
56	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage (DE): "weltweit größte deutschsprachige Volltext-Literatursammlung"	Homepage
57	online	CC BY-4.0	NaN	Download link: https://figshare.com/ndownl	Commentary: designed for use in teaching and research	Homepage

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
				oader/files/3686778		
58	online	NaN	NaN	https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/	Commentary/Homepage: project aimed at "Making poetry available online as machine-readable data will open a great world of possibilities of linking, indexing and extracting new information." approx. 4 millionen verse lines, regarding to: https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/corpus-y-datasets/	Homepage
59	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: only available in Russian	Homepage
60	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: only available in Russian	Homepage
61	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: only available in Russian	Homepage
62	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: only available in Russian	Homepage
63	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: download of books and creation of collections possible with institutional login	Homepage
64	online	CC BY 4.0	NaN	NaN	Commentary: links to TROVE for newspaper scans: https://trove.nla.gov.au/ ; corpus download as zip file	Homepage
65	online	NaN	NaN	https://data.cervantesvirtua.l.com/?_ga=2.19868668.55021663.1655726653-1879338039.1655467666	Commentary: corpus downloads available	Homepage

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
66	online	Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication, EUPL v1.2. License	NaN	https://github.com/europeana/	Homepage: "cultural heritage material from over 4,000 different institutions"	Homepage
67	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: corpus partly available for download	Homepage
68	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: The Bibliothèque nationale de France offers a Gallica iOS and Android application, can be downloaded for free	Homepage
69	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage (translated from Slovak): The Digital Library and Digital Archive (DIKDA) was the largest digitisation project in Slovakia and its scope was unique in the context of the European region. It was successfully implemented by the Slovak National Library between 2012 and 2015. Its aim was the high-quality mass digitisation of library and archive collections and the preservation of written cultural heritage (paper) from inevitable degradation.	Homepage
70	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: people can help edit works (zfeedit)	Homepage
71	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage
72	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage, search catalogue

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfInformation
73	online	from public to BY-NC-SA	NaN	http://fbc.pionier.net.pl/pr/o/en/	NaN	Homepage, search catalogue
74	online	NaN	NaN	https://github.com/opentexts/opentexts/	Commentary: Search engine; searches many other corpora, such as HaithiTrust, Cambridge University Library, DigitalNZ, etc., see: https://opentexts.world/about	Homepage
75	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: all texts are also available via project gutenberg;; download of TEI & plain text files: calls for a google-account	Homepage
76	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	Homepage
77	online	NaN	NaN	https://www.mqdq.it/public/c/corpora#HI_anchor	NaN	Homepage
78	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: subcorpus of MQDQ (line 78)	Homepage
79	online	NaN	NaN	Perseus Hopper: https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/opensource	Commentary: Perseus also hosts other collections: https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/collections ; some texts can be downloaded	Homepage
80	online	NaN	NaN	https://transkribus.eu/r/noscemus/#/statiDirectory	NaN	Wiki, Homepage NOSCEMUS

D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats

id	websiteStatus	corpusLicence	corpusReview	additionalLink	additionalInfo / commentary	sourceOfIn formation
81	online	CC BY 4.0	NaN	https://github.com/nevenjovanovic/lattycs/tree/1.1.10	Commentary: downloads possible	Homepage
82	online	NaN	NaN	http://www.ffzg.unizg.hr/klafil/dokuwiki/doku.php/z:croatia-et-tyrolensia	Comentary: hardly any information on corpus available on homepage; project description see: http://www.ffzg.unizg.hr/klafil/doku.php/z:croatia-et-tyrolensia	Homepage
83	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: PhiloLogic4	Homepage
84	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: downloads as PDFs	Homepage
85	online	NaN	NaN	NaN	Commentary: downloads possible	Homepage
86	online	CC-BY-SA-4.0	NaN	https://github.com/nevenjovanovic/came-na-neolatinlit/tree/v0.0.1	Commentary: contains five collections: POEMATA, Neo-Latin poetry composed by German authors; HISTORICA & POLITICA, Latin historical and political writing; THESAURUS ERUDITIONIS, a reference collection of dictionaries and handbooks of the period 1500-1750; CERA, printed Latin letters, mostly by German scholars, from the period 1530-1770; and ITALI, works by Italian Renaissance humanists born before 1500. The collection ITALI has no XML files, so it was not included in this repository.; downloads possible	Homepage